

> DESIRE6G <

D3.2: Interim report on the DESIRE6G intelligent and secure management, orchestration, and control

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Abstract

This document summarizes the first 23 months of work in work package 3, presenting the present development of the architecture of the DESIRE6G Service and Management Orchestrator, along with its components and the technologies used to achieve flexible and intelligent service instantiation and management on a 6G network. This document is an extension of D3.1 [1] with the implementation of the DESIRE6G secure management, orchestration, and control platform carried out so far.

Keywords

SMO, MAS, Intent-based translation, DLT federation, Security, Policy

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List of Acronyms

AWET	Absolute Weight Transformation
AMI	Adjusted Mutual Information
ARI	Adjusted Rand Index
AD	Administrative Domain
AF	Application Function
API	Application Programming Interface
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AAS	Asset Administration Shell
C-V2N	Cellular Vehicular-to-Network
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CAV	Connected Automated Vehicles
CNST	Constant
CSP	Content-Security-Policy
CP	Control Plane
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
DDPG	Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient
DHPG	Deep Hybrid Policy Gradient
DNN	Deep Neural Network
DRL	Deep Reinforcement Learning
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
E2E	End-to-End
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
FA	Failure Actuator
FEDAVG	Federated Averaging
FL	Federated Learning

FGOR	Fixed Gradient over Rays
GRU	Gated-Recurrent Unit
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GUI	Graphical User Interface
Grpc	gRPC Remote Procedure Calls
INT	In-band Network Telemetry
I4.0	Industry 4.0
IML	Infrastructure Management Layer
IMF	Intent Management Function
IBN	Intent-based Network
IRM	Invariant Risk Minimization
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LLM	Large Language Model
LSTM	Long-Short Term-Memory
ML	Machine Learning
MLFO	Machine Learning Function Orchestrator
MANO	Management and Orchestration
MDP	Markov Decision Process
MLaaS	ML as a Service
MAS	Multiagent System
NLP	Natural Language Processing
nRT	near-RT
NF	Network Function
NFV	Network Function Virtualization

NS	Network Services
NN	Neural Network
OGD	Online Gradient Descent
O-RAN	Open Radio Access Network
OE	Optimization Engine
PS	Parameter Server
PoP	Points of Presence
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PAA	Probability-as-Action
PDP	Programmable Data Plane
PI	Proportional and Integral
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
RT	Real-Time
RADE	Real-time Adaptive DEcomposition
RX	Receive
RIS	Reflecting Intelligent Surface
RL	Reinforcement Learning
REST	Representational State Transfer
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RADG	Retrieval-Augmented Generation
RoT	Root of Trust
SDO	Standards Development Organizations
SECaaS	SECurity-as-a-Service
SLSQP	Sequential Least Squares Programming
SLO	Service Level Objective
SMO	Service Management and Orchestration

SO	Service Orchestrator
SLA	Service-Level Agreement
SP	Shortest Path
S3	Simple Storage Service
SC	Smart Contract
SDN	Software-Defined Networking
ToC	Table of Content
TX	Transmit
TCP	Transport Control Protocol
TN	Transport Network
TES	Triple Exponential Smoothing
TD3	Twin Delayed Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications
V2I	Vehicle-to-Infrastructure
V2N	Vehicle-to-Network
V2P	Vehicle-to-Pedestrian
V2V	Vehicle-to-Vehicle
VXLAN	Virtual eXtensible Local Area Network
VIM	Virtual Infrastructure Manager
VNF	Virtual Network Function
WSS	Wavelength Selective Switch
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This document extends D3.1 [1] with greater emphasis on the implementation of the DESIRE6G secure management, orchestration, and control, carried out during the period of month 12 to month 23. We start by discussing the choices for artificial intelligence (AI)/ machine learning (ML) components at each layer. Next, the implementation details are documented under three major sections: (a) End-to-End (E2E) service management and orchestration (SMO), (b) Service optimization and assurance and (c) Robust, sustainable, and privacy preserving artificial intelligence/ machine learning. Finally, we discuss the regulatory aspects of the AI/ML approaches.

In contrast to D3.1 [1], the current deliverable includes a substantial discussion of the implementation of DESIRE6G architecture, underlying AI/ML components, and related algorithms. In addition, the alignment of AI/ML components to different layers of the architecture and the key reasons for the choices of respective AI/ML tools in each layer are clearly explained. Moreover, the AI/ML algorithm choices are almost finalized and the respective developments and implementations are well-defined compared to the initial developments documented in [1]. As such, a new section in this document is solely dedicated to present an initial study of the regulatory aspects of the algorithms. A more comprehensive discussion will be presented in D3.3 [2]. In this document, we have exhaustively referred to the published research articles, where the developments and implementations of our solution approaches are well compared with the state-of-the-art (SoA). Thus, we do not explicitly dedicate a separate section in this document to compare SoA. Such a detailed discussion is deferred to the final documentation D3.3 [2]. In the sequel, we highlight the key contributions of this document.

Key contributions are summarized below:

- We describe concisely our choices of AI/ML techniques with their mapping to the DESIRE6G architecture proposed in [3], see section 2.
- We describe the implementation details for:
 1. E2E SMO in Intent based Orchestration layer, see section 3 and references [4] [5] [6] [7] [8] [9] [10] [11] [12] [13] [14] [15] [16].

2. MAS in Optimization and Network Control layer, see section 4 and references [17] [18] [19] [20] [21] [22] [23] [24] [25] [26].
 3. AI integration, see section 5 and references [4] [5] [17] [20] [21] [27] [28] [29] [30] [31] [32] [33] [34].
- We have a preliminary study to discuss to what extent the choices of AI/ML approaches are compatible with related regulatory aspects, see section 6.

1. Introduction

During the period M12-M23 of the project, the involved partners in WP3 have been working on the further extension and implementation of the ML algorithms using the design of the AI-enabled service management and orchestration layer, as well as the secure MAS approach of the DESIRE6G architecture. Working closely with the partners involved in WP2 which defines the requirements and the overall architecture, implementation of the relevant components has been carried out.

We have concisely presented our choices of AI/ML technologies together with their relevance to the DESIRE6G architecture, see section 2. The choices of AI technologies are solely based on the study of their potential to meet the design specifications and the mapping of design specifications given in D2.1 [35] to the DESIRE6G architecture proposed in D2.2 [3].

It is worth recalling that the DESIRE6G architecture is layered into four main sections in accordance with the intended service requirements [35] [3]. In particular, the main layers include 1) Intent based Orchestration layer, 2) Optimization and Network Control layer, 3) E2E Programmable Data Plane layer, and 4) Physical Infrastructure layer. Moreover, each layer includes carefully chosen AI/ML technologies as an integral component to effectively realize the intended service requirements.

Intent-based orchestration layer mainly comprises the SMO framework is responsible for the orchestration, lifecycle management, and automation of E2E network services (NSs), aligning with specifications such as open radio access network (O-RAN) and European telecommunications standards institute (ETSI) management and orchestration (MANO). The DESIRE6G SMO introduces innovations including ML-powered intent-based networking (IBN), machine learning function orchestrator (MLFO), NS federation using distributed ledger technology (DLT), and data management and exposure services. Detailed implementation details of E2E SMO are documented in section 3. The key AI/ML component integrated within the intent-based orchestration layer is the Optimization Engine (OE), which is located at SMO. The goal of the intelligence in this respect is to decompose efficiently the E2E service-level agreements (SLAs) into partial SLAs for each segment (e.g., radio access network (RAN), transport) and optimize service graph partitioning based on neural networks trained with appropriately defined cost functions, where the operations would otherwise incur a formidable amount of computational

complexity hindering online system operations, see section 5 for implementation details. Notably, the OE is designed to be versatile, enabling its use for broader optimization tasks related to non-real-time control loops.

Optimization and network control layer contains the control plane (CP) logic and optimization logic [3]. Optimization logic is achieved by the MAS, which receives service-specific monitoring information and fine-tunes the network and compute resources to meet service requirements. Implementation details of MAS related components are documented in section 4. Moreover, it is worth highlighting that MAS implements distributed network intelligence closer to the physical infrastructure to meet near-RT (nRT) service requirements. The nRT control of 6G NSs requires decision-making to be placed as close to network devices as possible. As such, the solution of DESIRE6G is to deploy a distributed system with intelligent agents that relieves the classical centralized control plane from such nRT control loops. Because distributing decision-making entails new vulnerabilities that attackers can exploit, the distributed DESIRE6G control solution includes secure communications, as well as remote attestation to verify agents' integrity, both supported by immutable transactions based on a blockchain system. Associated AI/ML algorithm implementation is discussed in section 5.

E2E programmable data plane (PDP) layer related functionalities and implementation details are the subject of WP4, and thus extraneous to the focus of this deliverable. On the other hand, the physical infrastructure layer contains the computing and networking components of the DESIRE6G system including edge devices. AI/ML integration at edge is also considered, where the goal is to improve the efficiency of solution approaches for computationally challenging radio resource allocation problems, see section 5.

We note that the integration of AI/ML is foundational and intrinsic to the AI-native DESIRE6G architecture, shaping its design and functionality across all layers. Specifically, AI components that are integrated into the SMO enable effective non real-time decision making from a higher level. In contrast, the AI/ML integration at MAS in the optimization and network control layer permits the reconfigurations to be performed in an near real-time scale. At the edge the decisions are extremely fast since the decisions typically include, for instance, predictions based on pretrained neural networks (NNs). The entirety of AI integration developed in different layers of the architecture is based on almost all types of

key ML technologies including supervised learning, unsupervised learning, and reinforcement learning (RL), see section 2 and 5. Standardization and regulatory aspects of the proposed AI-native architecture can range from topics, including data privacy, safety and trustworthiness of the algorithms, reliability of the algorithms, and the lack of global standards themselves. A concise study in this respect is documented in section 6.

2. Alignment of AI Components with System Architecture

The DESIRE6G system architecture outlined in [3] is depicted in Figure 1 for ease of cross-referencing. Recall that the contributions of work package (WP) 3 encompass the first two layers of the architecture (i.e., Intent-Based Orchestration layer, the Optimization and Network Control layer), as well as the AI integration throughout all layers. As such, this section presents the details of the mapping of AI/ML components to the architecture. We note that the details of the mapping of design specifications in general to all the layers of the architecture within the scope of WP3 are deferred to D3.3 [2]. Moreover, we note that the related discussion of the PDP layer is not within the scope of this deliverable and thus refer the reader to D4.2 [36] for details.

FIGURE 1 HIGH LEVEL ARCHITECTURE.

Propelled by the AI integration requirements, we start by carefully identifying and aligning suitable AI technologies to meet the design specifications pertaining to E2E Service Orchestration requirements, Autonomous Networking requirements, Programmable Data Plane requirements, and Pervasive Monitoring requirements at different layers of the architecture (see [2] for details). As a result, we yield the mapping of AI components to the architecture of DESIRE6G, which is concisely depicted in Figure 2, together with the respective WPs within which the AI developments are carried out. Note that some

complementary AI tools are directly implemented in the Physical infrastructure layer as well. Details are summarized in the rest of this section.

FIGURE 2 MAPPING OF AI/ML COMPONENTS TO THE LAYERS OF THE ARCHITECTURE.

2.1. Aligning AI/ML Components to Intent Based Orchestration Layer

The Intent Based Orchestration Layer is mainly dedicated to E2E service orchestration requirements [2]. As such, to fulfill E2E Service Orchestration requirements, it is identified that the operations are penalized unless the two key operations, SLA decomposition and service graph partitioning, are carried out efficiently. These optimization problems are inherently combinatorial. Therefore, the main disadvantage of traditional solution approaches [37] for SLA decomposition and service graph partitioning is the scalability and the latencies incurred when solving the problems optimally or sub-optimally. These issues are circumvented by using AI/ML approaches that fall under *supervised learning* settings with neural networks. More specifically, appropriately chosen neural networks, such as deep neural networks (DNNs) and large language models (LLMs) or a combination of those for inferring the solutions to the optimization problems are trained with labelled datasets based on historical experiences. Findings are published in [5] [4]. Adequately trained ML models for these combinatorial

problems have the advantage of producing fast yet reasonable solutions. As such, they are indeed suitable for online decision-making offering more efficient resource allocation and optimization for use cases with stringent requirements, e.g., use cases that rely on ultra-reliable low latency communications (URLLC). In addition, based on estimations of carefully defined inference errors already learned models can be further refined making them more resilient to changes in the underlying settings. Details of algorithms and their implementations are given in section 5.1, see [4] [5] for original research articles.

2.2. Aligning AI/ML Components to Optimization and Network Control Layer

The Optimization and Network Control Layer oversees autonomous networking requirements. Therefore, there is an overwhelming need to enhance the network capabilities with provisions for nRT network reconfigurations since the underlying dynamics (e.g., traffic conditions) are very complex, changing, and even unpredictable. Under such intricate network conditions, it is impractical to train AI/ML models simply based on supervised learning techniques, since the collection of a dataset that is both correct and representative of all the underlying network situations is almost impossible. As such, an AI agent should be capable of learning from its own experience, and thus the most suitable AI technology in this regard is identified as RL. Consequently, multi-agent RL models based on deep reinforcement learning (DRL), deep deterministic policy gradient (DDPG), and deep hybrid policy gradient (DHPG) are used in network reconfiguration and scaling mechanisms for meeting autonomous networking requirements. Section 5.2 details the related algorithms. See [17] [18] [19] [20] [21] for original articles.

2.3. Aligning AI/ML Components to Programmable Data Plane Layer

Details related to PDP layer are not directly discussed within the scope of WP3, see Figure 2. We refer the reader to D4.2 [36] for a detailed description of those components. However, it is worth highlighting that the pervasive monitoring system, represented in Figure 2 by the block pervasive monitoring

requirements, is responsible for feeding almost all AI/ML algorithms during their training and deployment phases.

2.4. Complementary AI Tools in Physical Infrastructure Layer

AI tools have also been investigated that are to be intertwined with the Physical Infrastructure Layer. For instance, edge intelligence has been incorporated based on federated learning (FL) techniques for training neural network models that are capable of computing fast phase configuration for reflecting intelligent surface (RIS)-enabled wireless communication settings, where the solutions would otherwise be computationally intensive [27]. Moreover, the SoA approach, such as Federated Averaging (FEDAVG) [38], is known to perform poorly when the data is heterogeneous across agents. This is due to the fact that FEDAVG and its variants rely on an intrinsic assumption of identically distributed data. To address the issue of heterogeneity, some robust optimization frameworks have been introduced in the literature under some worst-case fairness criteria [39]. However, worst-case designs are usually over-conservative. In contrast, we designed our NN architectures within an Invariant Risk Minimization (IRM) [40], so that the resulting NN generalizes better its inferences than the other methods. Software implementations are documented in [28]. Some theoretical studies have also been conducted for certain performance characterization of FL algorithmic settings with a greater emphasis on inexact communication, graph optimization, and step size schedule characterization [32] [33] [34]. In addition, solution approaches based on unsupervised learning techniques such as principal component analysis (PCA) have been conducted to develop novel confidentiality-preserving techniques for data in a context where a third party is in charge of performing the data processing [30]. Moreover, research conducted by using real-time telemetry data for deploying forecasting ML components at edge, where Long-Short Term-Memory (LSTM)-NNs have been a natural choice due to ability to capture temporal dependencies of the time series data [31]. Section 5.3 presents details of related AI/ML algorithms.

3. E2E Service Management and Orchestration

One of the key objectives of WP3 is to design and implement a highly efficient End-to-End Service Orchestration system within the DESIRE6G framework. The focus is to enable seamless deployment and lifecycle management of services across a heterogeneous, multi-domain 6G environment. One of the key components to achieve this is the SMO. Related opensource developments and implementations are available at [7] [8] [9] [10] [11] [12] [13] [14] [15] [16].

Additional components include the secure MAS, along with AI/ML algorithms that facilitate service instantiation and re-configuration. These elements are essential for achieving secure, scalable, and autonomous service orchestration in DESIRE6G's cloud-native architecture.

3.1. DESIRE6G SMO

The design of the DESIRE6G SMO is described in D3.1 [1] and D2.2 [3]. This section provides additional details regarding the implementation of the SMO, along with the challenges related to both design choices and implementation limitations.

3.1.1. SMO Implementation

The implementation of the SMO leverages a modular, microservice-based architecture, to enable scalability and easy management. This design allows each component of the SMO to operate independently, providing flexibility for updates, scalability, and independent deployment. A key feature of this architecture is the integration of sandboxed container runtimes, such as kata-containers, which ensure secure multi-tenancy. This approach aligns with cloud-native principles, supporting both workload isolation and security on shared infrastructure. In Task 3.1, significant advancements have been made to implement this architecture. The key components of the SMO, along with their implementations are described in the rest of this section.

3.1.1.1 Service Orchestrator

The Service Orchestrator coordinates and manages the lifecycle of services, handling tasks such as deployment, deletion, and listing of active services. It enables secure and modular service management, coordinating with the DESIRE6G Sites (e.g., through infrastructure management layer (IML)) to instantiate or terminate services as needed.

FastAPI [41] provides a RESTful [42] interface for creating, retrieving, and deleting service instances. The service orchestrator (SO) integrates with RabbitMQ [43] to receive and send messages to the bus, related to service status and updates, interacting with the rest of the SMO components. This component enables the instantiation of services and provides options to retrieve lists of all deployed services, as well as specific details for each one.

Related application programming interface (API) Endpoints are listed below with a brief description:

POST /service/: Deploys a new service by ID.

Request Body JavaScript Object Notation (JSON):

```
{
  "service_id": "string",
  "site_id": "string"
}
```

Description: Deploys a service to a specific site, based on the provided IDs.

DELETE /service/{service_id}: Deletes a deployed service.

Description: Removes a specific service instance based on its unique service_id.

GET /deployed_services: Lists all currently deployed services.

Response (JSON):

```
[
  {
    "service_id": "string",
    "name": "string",
    "status": "string"
  },
  ...
]
```

Description: Provides a summary of all active services.

GET /deployed_services/{service_id}: Retrieves details of a specific deployed service by service_id.

```
{
  "service_id": "string",
  "name": "string",
  "status": "string",
  "details": {...}
}
```

Description: Returns information about a specific deployed service.

3.1.1.2 Topology

The Topology component is responsible for maintaining and updating the network and service topology, which includes tracking nodes (DESIRE6G sites) and their resources. It allows for the addition and retrieval of nodes, providing essential data for deployment and resource management decisions.

The component uses FastAPI to expose a RESTful API, which supports easy integration with other services. Data about nodes, such as central processing unit (CPU), memory, and storage, is stored in a database, which the Topology component can query and update. A RabbitMQ interface facilitates asynchronous notifications to other services, informing them of any updates to the topology.

Related API Endpoints follow:

POST /nodes/: Adds a new node to the database.

Request Body (JSON):

```
{
  "site_id": "string",
  "cpu": "string",
  "memory": "string",
  "storage": "string",
  "iml_endpoint": "string"
}
```

Description: Stores node data, including the site ID, the IML endpoint and resource details.

GET /nodes/{site_id}: Retrieves node information by site_id.

Response (JSON):

```
{
  "site_id": "string",
  "cpu": "string",
  "memory": "string",
  "storage": "string",
  "iml_endpoint": "string"
}
```

Description: Retrieve information about a specific node, based on its ID.

3.1.1.3 Service Catalog

The Service Catalog acts as the registry for available services within the D6G platform. It stores service configurations, primarily in YAML format, which define how services should be deployed and configured. This catalog enables easy discovery and management of services within the architecture.

Using FastAPI, this component offers endpoints for storing and retrieving service definitions. Service configurations are stored in YAML format, making them easy to manage and version. RabbitMQ provides asynchronous notifications for updates, enabling real-time catalog synchronization.

Related API Endpoints are listed below:

POST /store: Stores a YAML graph in the catalog

Response (JSON):

```
{
  "name": "string",
  "data": "YAML_string"
}
```

Description: Saves a service definition or configuration under a specific name.

POST /upload: Uploads a YAML file to the catalog.

Request (File Upload): The uploaded file must have a .sg.yaml or .nf.yaml extension.

Example CURL Command:

```
curl -X POST -F "file=@/path/to/your/service_graph.sg.yaml"
http://localhost:8000/upload/
```

Description: Stores a YAML file on the server for future retrieval.

GET /file/{file_name}: Retrieves the contents of a YAML file by its file_name.

Example CURL Command:

```
curl http://localhost:8000/file/example\_file.yaml
```

Description: Returns the content of the specified YAML file.

GET /list_files: Lists all YAML files currently stored in the server's storage.

Example CURL Command:

```
curl http://localhost:8000/list\_files
```

Description: Provides a list of available YAML files, allowing clients to see all stored service configurations

3.1.1.4 Data Lake

The Data Lake is a versatile repository structured to support the specialized data needs of its cloud and edge. It is optimized to store and manage both large datasets and operational insights, centralizing the information flow to support enhanced analytics, ML, and system-wide optimization.

S3 Storage is dedicated to housing ML models and large data blobs, ensuring scalable, high-performance storage for sizable, static assets. This approach allows the DESIRE6G platform to store and manage data that does not require real-time processing but is essential for training, retraining, and deploying ML models across the platform. By storing models centrally, the DESIRE6G system can deploy and update ML capabilities to nodes at all levels of the continuum as new models become available, ensuring adaptive, data-driven intelligence throughout the network.

Telemetry Ingestion is managed through a separate, high-frequency streaming endpoint using Prometheus and Kafka. This endpoint is responsible for real-time telemetry data, relaying telemetry from all nodes, including CPU and memory availability, usage, and latency. Prometheus manages time-series data, providing a historical record of system performance, while Kafka handles the high-throughput streaming necessary for event-based data, facilitating continuous, near-instantaneous updates, and

replication across all sites. This structured telemetry layer feeds analytics engines and real-time AI models within the DESIRE6G continuum, enabling closed-loop decision-making.

The Container Image Registry endpoint acts as a dedicated endpoint within the Data Lake for storing and managing container images. This repository is essential for providing service, network and application functions that are to be deployed in DESIRE6G. With this approach, all nodes have entire access to up-to-date software and services.

3.1.2. Internal and External Interfaces

The SMO is built with both internal and external interfaces, each facilitating specific types of communication and data flow within and outside the SMO environment.

3.1.2.1 Internal Interfaces

Internal interfaces handle communication between SMO components. They enable the flow of information within the SMO, allowing each microservice to function effectively while contributing to the system's overall goals.

Message Queue (RabbitMQ):

The message queue is the backbone of internal communication within the SMO, providing asynchronous communication between components. This setup is essential for a distributed microservices architecture, as it decouples services, allowing them to communicate without needing to be aware of each other's implementation specifics.

Both the IBN component and the Optimization Engine rely on real-time data to perform optimizations and enforce intents. The message queue enables these components to receive up-to-date information about the network state, topology changes, service deployments, and performance metrics from other parts of the SMO. For instance, the Optimization Engine can subscribe to performance and resource data, analyzing it for optimization decisions.

The message queue supports both synchronous and asynchronous communication, which is crucial for handling tasks with different latency and criticality requirements. It manages events like service state updates, alerts, and topology changes, propagating them efficiently.

Data Model:

A shared data model standardizes the format for information exchanged between services, including JSON and YAML for configurations, metrics, and telemetry. Consistent data formats reduce parsing errors and facilitate smooth data exchange, allowing services like the Data Lake to store and retrieve information accurately. Each service exposes REST API endpoints (using FastAPI), which other services within the SMO can call. These endpoints allow services like the Service Orchestrator, Topology Manager, and Service Catalog to interact directly for operations that require immediate confirmation or response, such as retrieving node data or deploying new services.

Sync/Async Communication:

The SMO uses synchronous communication for requests that need immediate responses (e.g., querying a specific node's details) and asynchronous communication for tasks that can be processed in the background (e.g., service deployment). This hybrid communication model provides flexibility, ensuring that essential operations are handled promptly while less critical tasks do not overload the system.

3.1.2.2 External Interfaces

External interfaces expose SMO functionalities to external entities, such as other network components, third-party applications, or users.

REST APIs:

REST APIs provide accessible endpoints for external systems to interact with SMO functionalities, such as retrieving network topology, managing service deployments, and accessing stored data in the Data Lake. External systems (e.g., OSS/BSS logic) can submit high-level intents via REST, which the SMO then translates into actionable tasks. External monitoring tools or control systems can request performance reports or optimization suggestions via the REST API.

Simple Storage Service (S3)-Compatible Storage:

For components that handle large datasets such as logs, configuration files, or telemetry data) the SMO might provide an S3-compatible interface for easy, scalable storage and retrieval. The Data Lake, for instance, uses an S3 interface to store and retrieve telemetry data generated by network devices or application performance logs.

Time-Series Data and Remote Procedure Calls (gRPC):

gRPC-based interfaces allow external systems to perform high-speed data retrievals for monitoring, logging, or analytics. Time-series data is essential for performance monitoring, and gRPC enables efficient real-time data streaming, which could be particularly useful for the Network Optimization Engine in detecting trends and adjusting configurations accordingly.

3.1.2.3 Message Queue (RabbitMQ) – A Deeper Look

The message queue's role extends beyond simple message passing. In the SMO, RabbitMQ is configured to handle different types of messages (topics) and allow specific components to subscribe or publish as needed.

The message queue enables the SMO to adopt an event-driven architecture, where components react to specific events (e.g., node addition, service deployment) in nRT. This is particularly useful for the IBN, which translates intents into network configurations, and the Network Optimization Engine, which relies on up-to-date data for effective optimization.

RabbitMQ allows each service to operate independently while still receiving updates. This decoupling is essential in microservices, ensuring that services like the Topology Manager or Service Orchestrator can update or deploy new services without interrupting other components.

RabbitMQ helps distribute workload among multiple instances of the same service, such as several instances of the Data Lake processing data storage and retrieval tasks. It improves the scalability and resilience of the SMO by distributing tasks evenly and handling high traffic during peak loads.

If a service fails, messages can be retained in queues until the service is back online. This guarantees that critical tasks (e.g., intent updates in IBN or optimization tasks) are not lost and are processed as soon as the service is available.

3.1.3. Challenges and limitations

In a microservices-based SMO, managing the complexity of interfaces poses a significant challenge. Each microservice may have unique requirements for data formatting, communication protocols, and request handling, leading to intricate and interdependent interfaces. This complexity becomes even more difficult to manage as the SMO scales, as services increasingly rely on coordinated communication to function correctly. Without the proper interface design and thorough testing, the system may suffer from data inconsistencies, delayed responses, or outright communication failures, all of which could impact the stability of the SMO. For instance, if the Topology Manager and Service Orchestrator services expect slightly different data formats, a mismatch could result in misinterpreted data, incorrect topology updates, or failed service deployments.

The scattered management that comes with a microservices-architecture is another challenge. Each service is deployed, monitored, and scaled independently, which adds flexibility but complicates centralized oversight and coordination. The need for independent lifecycle management for each service, from updates and monitoring to scaling and error handling, often leads to increased operational overhead. This can create challenges in troubleshooting and debugging, as tracking down the origin of issues may require insights from multiple services across the SMO.

Asynchronous communication, while enabling real-time, non-blocking interactions, also introduces potential delays and complexities in ensuring message consistency. Some operations depend on a series of events from other services, and without strict synchronization, delays in one service can cascade into delayed responses or missing data in others. For instance, if the Service Orchestrator depends on updates from the Topology Manager but receives them with a lag, it may inadvertently act on outdated data, affecting deployment accuracy.

The SMO must also address the demands of a multi-domain environment, where each component or module may involve different programming languages, data formats, and deployment environments.

This diversity requires interoperability solutions to bridge these gaps, adding complexity to both development and maintenance. Multi-domain challenges are particularly pronounced in telecom settings, where compliance and performance requirements often differ across network domains. For example, the Network Optimization Engine might rely on data formats that differ from those used by the Intent-Based Networking component, requiring translation or mapping mechanisms that add complexity and potential points of failure.

Together, these challenges highlight the complexity and need for well-coordinated, robust design in a microservices-based SMO, emphasizing the importance of clear interfaces, strict synchronization, and careful attention to interoperability across all SMO components. To address the challenges and limitations inherent in a microservices-based SMO, several mitigation techniques can be employed. These techniques aim to enhance the system's robustness, improve efficiency, and ensure the seamless operation of services while maintaining flexibility and scalability.

To mitigate the complexity of managing interfaces between microservices, one of the most effective strategies is to define clear API contracts. This means establishing well-documented, standardized formats for data exchanges between services. By using open standards like RESTful APIs and JSON or YAML for data interchange, we reduce mismatches and ensure smooth communication.

Moreover, employing automated integration tests can prevent interface issues before they arise in production. These tests can verify that each service can communicate as expected with other services, catching problems early in the development cycle.

To address the challenges posed by scattered service management, we employ centralized service orchestration. This involves using Kubernetes which manages the lifecycle of services across the system. Kubernetes automates deployment, scaling, and operation of containerized services, simplifying management and allowing services to be updated or replaced without impacting the whole system. For monitoring and alerting, we use Prometheus and Grafana, that provide real-time insights into the health and performance of individual services, helping us identify and resolve issues quickly.

Furthermore, centralized logging to the Data Lake, allows us to trace requests and identify failures in such a complex distributed system. This helps mitigate the difficulties of troubleshooting in a scattered microservices environment.

Mitigating delays and inconsistencies in asynchronous communication is achieved through message queue management strategies. Using RabbitMQ in combination with message acknowledgements ensures that messages are reliably delivered and processed, reducing the risk of data loss or out-of-order processing. Additionally, dead-letter queues capture messages that fail to be processed, enabling a mechanism for recovery without loss of critical data.

To further reduce potential delays, service prioritization is implemented. We define priority levels for different types of communication, ensuring that critical operations (such as service deployment or intent updates) are processed more urgently than less time-sensitive tasks. Event-driven architecture is also employed to ensure that the system only processes events that are relevant to the current context, avoiding unnecessary load on the system.

Dealing with multiple domains, languages, and deployment environments requires careful design of interoperability layers. Using middleware services that translate and map data between different formats and protocols ensures smooth communication between heterogeneous systems. In cases where different microservices use various technologies (e.g., Python, Go, Java), leveraging common communication standards such as gRPC allows disparate systems to communicate more effectively.

Additionally, containerization ensures that each service runs in a consistent environment, regardless of the underlying infrastructure, and tools like Helm help us package and deploy services in a standardized manner. This reduces friction in cross-domain interactions by providing consistent deployment strategies. For systems that rely on real-time, high-throughput communication like our SMOs, ensuring scalability and reliability is crucial. A combination of auto-scaling using tools like Kubernetes HPA and load balancing ensures that the system can dynamically adjust to varying loads. Kubernetes can automatically scale services based on demand, ensuring that the system remains responsive even as workloads fluctuate. Similarly, retry mechanisms are introduced to handle transient failures and ensure eventual consistency in communication.

3.2. Optimization Engine

This section introduces the OE, a key module of the SMO framework, specifically implemented for generic optimizations. For instance, for service deployment, the OE interacts directly with the SO, mainly

it expects unoptimized service graphs, annotated with end-to-end SLAs or objectives. Leveraging machine learning and artificial intelligence techniques, the OE performs service graph partitioning, providing the SO with partial Service Graphs annotated with their respective partial Service Level Objectives (SLOs). This section presents our initial development blocks of OE.

3.2.1. AI/ML Workflow

The workflow of the module (see Figure 3) is based on 5 simple steps: (1) Receiving an unoptimized annotated graph from the IBN, (2) Selecting the correct model from the model pool, based on the annotation, (3) execute optimization with the selected model, (4) deliver the optimized service back to the SO, and finally (5) evaluate models periodically based on feedback from the SMO. The OE SMO module optimizes service graphs to provide lower latency, higher availability, energy efficiency, privacy, or any SLA to the services deployed with the DESIRE6G platform.

FIGURE 3: OPTIMIZATION ENGINE AI/ML ARCHITECTURE.

3.2.2. Encoding/Decoding and Processing Service Requests

The OE receives an unoptimized service graph from the SO in the standardized and predefined JSON format which serves as an input for the optimization subprocess. Upon receiving the unoptimized service graph, the OE decodes, stores the annotated information and pre-processes it using a dedicated routine, preparing the data for the graph optimization.

Following the partitioning phase, the OE performs encoding on the resulting optimized and partitioned service graphs, ensuring they are compatible with the end-to-end requirements. Finally, OE applies post-processing to verify the output before returning the optimized service graph(s) to the SO in its /their encoded format.

3.2.3. Model Pool

The AI/ML Model Pool is a collection of AI models that can be used for service (graph) optimization. These models are designed to operate based on distinct key performance indicators (KPIs). For example, for the main use case scenario, a graph partitioning model can be used to minimize E2E latency. Each model targets a specific aspect of performance, enabling that way an efficient and optimized service delivery based on the network conditions.

3.2.4. Model Management and Selection

The AI Model Management Component is a collection of tools that analyze the received service descriptions, and performs the model selection, based on LLMs. It is also responsible for the model performance evaluation after the actuation, giving feedback to the internal mechanism to fine-tune the selection process.

3.2.5. Optimization Subsystem Implementation

The OE is designed with modularity in mind. It is comprised of various submodules built using Python 3.12, allowing for flexibility and maintainability. A well-defined API enables seamless communication with the other SMO modules. Furthermore, the OE features a graphical user interface (GUI), developed

as a Web Application that allows the administrator to fine-tune and supervise the optimization process in a non-text-based manner. Additionally, the OE supports plug-and-play optimization models and algorithms, allowing quick experimentation and selection of the most suitable ones for specific use cases.

3.3. IBN Management

This section provides an overview of the SLA-to-Intent Translator and IBN functions in DESIRE6G, expanding on the concepts from deliverable [1] with additional details on the architecture and workflows.

FIGURE 4 SLA-TO-INTENT TRANSLATION FRAMEWORK.

3.3.1. SLA-to-Intent Translation

In this section, we will outline the key components of the SLA-to-intent translation framework, detailing the operational steps and processes involved. The translation comprises three main functions and an API interface as illustrated in Figure 4. At the current stage, the use case requirement has been written in free text format as SLA. The actual SLA format is still an ongoing work.

These functions include extracting essential metrics and service information from SLAs, normalizing this data into a standardized tabular format to ensure consistency and support further processing, and preparing the intent form. Together, these steps facilitate effective translation from SLAs to actionable intents.

3.3.1.1 SLA Entrance and Intent Representation Interface

This endpoint takes SLA expression as input in Figure 5. The application is built using Python with Flask and JavaScript, utilizing RESTful APIs for communication with backend services. This setup allows for efficient interaction with SLA consumer and SLA-to-Intent translation framework. Key features include a login page, home page, menu, and Intent page, all designed for a user-friendly experience. The use of REST APIs ensures smooth data exchange, enhancing performance, and scalability for future integrations. This interface is designed for free text SLA form, and we also go on searching for alternative approaches.

Service Level Agreement

Type the legal and other issue in free text

.....

XR cell availability requirement:
XR availability must be more or equal than 99%.

UE Throughput requirement for :

- DL: average 45Mbps and if it is under 30 Mbps, the service will be accepted not to serve]
- UL: average 6 Mbps and if it is under 4 Mbps for, the service will be accepted not to serve]
- Measurement frequency: 5 times in one hour
- Penalty: %0.01 future outage

UE specific PDB requirement:
An XR UE is declared satisfied

- DL: 99% of application layer packets are successfully transmitted within 10 ms PDB
- UL: 99% of application layer packets are successfully transmitted within 20 ms PDB

in busy hours.

XR Cell capacity:

- XR capacity is defined as the maximum number of XR UEs per cell with at least 90% of these UEs being satisfied.

FIGURE 5 SAMPLE XR USE CASE SLA.

3.3.1.2 Gen AI for Exporting Key Metrics from SLA and Creation of Intent

The application operates through a structured process designed to deliver relevant and high-quality text. Initially, it queries a vector database to identify documents that align with the user's intent expressed in the input string. Once pertinent documents are retrieved, the application employs LLM to generate text based on this information.

Vector databases play a crucial role in the functionality of LLMs by enabling the storage and efficient querying of high-dimensional vectors, including word embeddings, sentence embeddings, and document embeddings. This capability significantly enhances the performance of LLMs in several keyways..

One of the primary advantages of using vector databases is their ability to provide context. When LLMs are equipped with relevant contextual information about a topic, they can generate more accurate and pertinent text. Vector databases efficiently store diverse types of contextual data, which helps LLMs understand the nuances of language and topic relevance.

Vector databases also contribute to the accuracy of LLM predictions. By leveraging embeddings that have been learned from extensive and relevant text corpora, LLMs can be trained on more precise data. This training enhances their ability to produce reliable and context-aware responses, making them more effective for specific tasks.

Retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) is an innovative framework that merges two critical aspects of natural language processing: retrieval and generation. Widely used with LLMs, RAG enhances their capabilities and improves the quality of generated responses. Here's a closer look at its key components.

The retrieval component of RAG involves a mechanism that searches a predefined knowledge base or text corpus for pertinent information. Various methods can be employed for this search, ranging from traditional keyword searches to advanced techniques like semantic similarity and Dense Retrieval. The primary goal is to identify relevant content that will aid in generating coherent and contextually appropriate responses.

Once relevant information is retrieved, the generation component—typically powered by a language model—takes over. The language model uses the gathered information to produce natural language responses or completions. This ensures that the generated text is not only coherent but also contextually relevant, aligning closely with the user's needs.

We have divided the larger task and prompted LLM to provide a step-by-step extraction of information. The responses from previous prompts are utilized to create a more coherent and context-aware conversation. The final prompt employs a "few-shot approach" to generate a resource description framework (RDF) based on the information extracted in each step. To facilitate this, a few sample RDFs are provided as examples of the desired legal language or document structure for the LLM to learn from, allowing the model to generate similar content effectively.

3.3.1.3 Tabular Form for Normalization and Metric Check

In the realm of SLAs, clarity and consistency are paramount. We are searching for a comprehensive view by organizing the essential components of an SLA—such as keywords, measurement units, formulas, and constraints into a tabular format.

To enhance our understanding and implementation of SLAs, we have extended the ETSI table [44]. We extended table effectively captures all Service Level Objectives (SLOs) that may be included in an SLA, covering aspects before, during, and after service delivery. By categorizing Quality of Service (QoS) definitions into distinct sub-headings within the ETSI framework, we provide a nuanced understanding of service requirements. These categories include sales, service provisioning, service alteration/technical upgrade, service support, repair-troubleshooting, metering, charging and billing, cessation, service management by the customer, and service utilization.

This comprehensive structure enhances our understanding of QoS across various operational dimensions. The tabular representation encompasses fundamental quality metrics, including availability, integrity, time, and capacity, alongside integrated figures such as reliability. Moreover, it addresses specific needs through flexibility, usability, and security metrics.

Advanced Features of the Tabular Representation

The enhanced table introduces new columns for SLA type details, service name and type, SLA relationships (peer-to-peer or third-party), domain mappings (e.g., core network, transport network, RAN), process priorities, and relationships. KPI expectations are also included, specifying whether they are anticipated, mandatory, or optional as illustrated in Figure 6. Additionally, the table addresses penalties, formulations, geographical constraints, and conditions like business hours or weekends.

Parameter	QoS Availability			Parameter	QoS Time			Parameter	QoS Capacity		
	Worse	Average	Best		Worse	Average	Best		Worse	Average	Best
Availability	99%	99.9%	99.99%	PDB /Packet success rate				Uplink	4 Mbps	6 Mbps	20 Mbps
Mandatory/ Optional	Mandatory			Uplink		20 ms /99%	10 ms/99%	Downlink	30 Mbps	45 Mbps	60 Mbps
Measurement	Average over a week			Downlink		10 ms/99%	5 ms/99%	Mandatory/ Optional	Mandatory		
Time constraint	24/7			Mandatory/ Optional	Mandatory			Measurement	5 times in one hour		
Region	Urban							Time constraint	24/7		
								Region	Urban		
								Penalty	%0.01 future outage for each		
				Y2							
				Y3-1							
				Y3-2							
				Y4.1							
				Y4.2							
				Y4.3							
				Y4.4							
				Y5							
				Y6							
				Y7							
				Y8							
				Y9.1							
				Y9.2							
				Y9.3							
				Y9.4							

Service mark	Parameter	QoS Capacity
Expected value	%90	
Mandatory/ Optional	Mandatory	

FIGURE 6 XR SLA TABULAR REPRESENTATION.

3.3.1.4 Standardized Templates

To maintain quality, there is necessity for standardized tabular templates for different service types, aligned with 3GPP/GSMA standards and approved according to Content-Security-Policy (CSP) policies. These templates could play a vital role in preventing unrealistic expectations and poorly communicated values in SLAs. These tables, tagged according to their respective use cases, are maintained in JSON or YAML format. By comparing the new SLA metrics in the tabular representation with existing templates for similar services, we can ensure relevance and accuracy. When organized and named according to specific use cases, locating pertinent tables becomes straightforward.

An SLA ontology is a formal representation of concepts and relationships related to SLAs. It typically includes entities such as services, metrics, targets, penalties, and conditions. Once the ontology is created, SLA documents should be saved in a structured format based on the ontology. To compare two saved SLAs, the process can be automated using a programming language or an ontology comparison tool. This is an ongoing and unfinished study and therefore specific methods that should be incorporated in this regard have not yet been decided.

3.3.1.5 Revaluation and Feedback Mechanisms

Missed or unreasonable expectations can be reassessed and redefined using comparison codes and functions based on these templates. Alternatively, these concerns can be addressed through consultation with the SLA manager via a feedback mechanism. This process clarifies whether expectations are accurate or if discrepancies require resolution through natural language processing (NLP) techniques. Such reevaluation is essential before finalizing intentions, serving as a final check to ensure that values and expectations are properly aligned.

The intent is transmitted to the intent management function (IMF) using the SET API in RDF format. The SET method allows for the submission of new intent objects or the modification of existing ones at any time. Upon receipt, the intent handler responds immediately according to the REST protocol mechanism.

If the intent is unsupported, the response may indicate rejections due to unsupported expectations, unsupported information models, or issues considered out of scope. Additionally, the IMF might accept the intent but issue a warning if the handling process proves unsuccessful or other cases.

3.3.2. Intent Management Function

The IMF, often referred to as the intent manager, is an entity that autonomously manages a domain through intents. It accepts intents via its northbound interface, either from a human operator or another intent owner, and is responsible for executing these intents. The intent manager stores these intents as knowledge objects and makes independent decisions by monitoring the managed environment. Through its southbound interface, it provides another intents or actions.

The intent manager consists of a framework and software components with specific functions, known as agents. The intent manager framework comprises two main components: a knowledge base and a reasoning engine. The knowledge base stores various knowledge objects, including information about the managed environment, its current state, intents and their expectations, as well as domain models and expert insights. The reasoning engine is responsible for drawing inferences from this knowledge, generating new insights from existing information. It autonomously determines which agents to invoke to fulfill the intents, using both the stored intents and relevant data, including real-time measurements and historical records. These agents play various roles, such as data grounding, action proposing,

predicting, evaluating, and acting. The intent manager utilizes these agents to fulfill intents by implementing closed-loop processes.

The reasoner facilitates both forward and backward chaining (i.e., reasoning) through inference rules (for forward chaining) and relations (for backward chaining). The rules are effectively always active, being triggered when specific patterns emerge in the knowledge base. When activated, they can modify the knowledge base or carry out other actions, such as sending messages to agents.

FIGURE 7 INTENT MANAGEMENT FUNCTIONS.

An IMF receives intents which is essentially a set of expectations, which could be both delivery and property expectations. Each one is supported by a closed loop dedicated to its fulfillment. This closed loop consists of several agents, which the intent manager selects based on the knowledge stored in the knowledge base as shown in Figure 7.

Utility definitions are made to ensure the expectation of the intent are met, and the IMF strives to maximize this. Utility information can be used in the formulation that maps metric values to a utility score, which represents business value. Including this information in the intent, along with requirements expressed in the same metrics, enables the intent owner to communicate their perception of business value and preferences to the IMF. This approach quantifies the information, facilitating utility computation, optimization, and conflict resolution decisions. Utility-related information as a set of

knowledge facts to help IMF for deciding actions is an ongoing study. The types and responsibilities of agents are as follows:

- **Data grounding agents** are tasked with querying the network and processing data, ultimately storing the gathered information in the knowledge base. They collect raw data that represents the state of the managed environment, which is then processed and recorded as properties in the intent manager's knowledge base.
- **Goal setting agents:** These agents map issues with intent expectations to goals that the IMF needs to resolve.
- **Proposal agents:** These agents analyze the goals and propose one or more solutions.
- **Prediction agents:** These agents analyze the proposals from the Proposal agent and make predictions – based on information stored in the KB and with the help of the reasoner or AI/ML models – about the possible impact of the proposals on all the IMF services.
- **Evaluation agents:** These agents take the predictions from the prediction agents and select the more suitable action (e.g., by approving actions maximizing the global utility of the IMF; this global utility is understood as the utility of all the intents accepted by the IMF).
- **Actuation agents:** These agents receive approved actions from the Evaluation agents to implement the solution (e.g., direct actuation or intent setting).
- **Reporting agents:** These agents collect the reports from other IMFs and forward them to the reasoner.

3.3.3. Service Graph Generation Process

Service graph generation in IBN involves considering service functional requirements derived from high-level intents. Requirements extraction from intent can be achieved using domain ontology. The problem's input consists of initial services obtained from a domain ontology and a service catalog that provides information about services and their expected input/output contents. The output is a set of possible service graphs that can fulfill the functional requirements derived from user intent. A service graph is a directed graph comprising nodes and links, where the nodes represent functions, such as

Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) or microservice-based NFs, and the links represent the logical connections between them.

In the knowledge base, we assume that there are foundational service graphs for each service. The grounding agent will collect service catalog information based on the constraints provided by the intent. The proposal agent will use existing nodes and algorithms to find all combinations, which will then be presented to the intent manager. For these service graphs, requests will be sent to the optimization engine to match them with service KPIs, and the responses will be sent to the prediction agent to assess the impact on other services. The results will be evaluated by the evaluation agent, and based on the assessment of the service graph options and their effects, the final version of the service graph will be determined.

In the proposal agent, an algorithm systematically will build a compatible graph by exploring services from a starting point (sources), identifying compatible services through a service catalog, and ensuring that the resulting graph has only forward connections relevant to the desired destinations. It emphasizes maintaining a clean graph by removing backward edges, thus enhancing the structure and usability of the graph for further applications in service orchestration or networking tasks. First, the system will examine the compatibilities between services using information about the initial services derived from the translated intent and the service compatibilities outlined in the service catalog. Next, it will extract the candidate service graphs from the compatible graph generated in the first step. This will involve identifying all possible routes between the source and destination services within the compatible graph.

3.3.4. Intent Decomposition

Decomposing an intent involves breaking down each expectation into sub-intents and actions. These sub-intents are then assigned to different domain-specific IMFs that are equipped to manage them. When the sub-domain IMFs successfully execute the sub-intents along with the required actions, the overall intent is fulfilled. The decomposition tasks must be aware of the relationships between the targets and properties they can manage and those that their child IMFs can handle. Each IMF has access to this knowledge.

Intent decomposition can be performed using rule-based approaches, AI/ML methods, or other techniques, and this study is based on a rule-based approach. Rule-based optimization involves specifying rules for how decomposition should occur based on the probe data received. Rule-based techniques rely on algebraic formulations to decompose various service IMF expectations. These expectations can be effectively composed using specific composition rules. Depending on the metric, different rules apply. Latency is additive across the different decomposed IMFs, throughput is determined by the minimum value produced from the composition of IMFs, and availability is multiplicative across the IMFs.

Intent-driven systems enable automated interactions between intent owners and handlers on the intent interface during operation, allowing the IMFs to negotiate intent settings and processes. The "Judge" operation allows an intent handler to present multiple solution options to an intent owner for evaluation. Additionally, the "Probe" operation enables the intent owner to verify which expectations can realistically be met before formalizing the intent. The "Best" operation assesses the highest performance level the handler can achieve for given requirements, considering any constraints.

In DESIRE6G, decomposition will be performed on three layers: RAN, transport network (TN), and Core. The proposal agent requests the optimization engine to predict KPI levels for each domain based on the service chain. Additionally, it seeks the "Best" value expectations by asking the sub-layer IMFs to reoptimize.

The optimization engine sends expected KPI values to the proposal agent. Upon receiving all the values from the optimization engine, the proposal agent combines the results with the historical intent report values and grounding data to create a single intent decomposition proposal and forwards it to the reasoner.

The reasoner subsequently asks the evaluation agent to evaluate the predicted decomposition proposal. Once the evaluation agent approves the proposal, the reasoner instructs the actuation agent to implement the decomposition actions. The actuation agent's next task is to create intent requests for the lower-level IMF via the SET API.

3.4. DLT Federation

This section provides an overview of the DLT-based federation mechanism in DESIRE6G, expanding on the concepts from deliverable D3.1 [1] with additional details on the architecture and workflows [6].

3.4.1. Overview of DLT-Based Federation in SMO

Figure 8 illustrates a simplified representation of the DESIRE6G architecture designed to support DLT-based federation as part of the SMO feature set. The architecture leverages blockchain technology and smart contracts to enable highly secure, private, fast and distributed interactions between administrative domains (ADs) in the federation process. Implementing federation procedures on a public permissionless blockchain can be expensive due to high transaction fees, whereas the implementation and maintenance costs of a permissioned blockchain are lower. Moreover, permissioned blockchains provide faster processing times, as they involve fewer participants and more efficient consensus protocols, while allowing restrictions on network participation (e.g., limiting the kind of transactions) [6]. Given the security and efficiency requirements of mobile network infrastructures, permissioned access is preferred. Hence, our design adopts a non-customized (i.e., a vanilla) version of a permissioned blockchain network (e.g., private Ethereum, Hyperledger, Cosmos, etc.), where each domain (i.e., service provider with SMO infrastructure) runs a single blockchain node connected to the Eastbound interface/Westbound interface of the SMO. By adding and registering a node, administrative domains gain access to the permissioned blockchain network. The distributed nature of the blockchain network ensures scalability while maintaining security.

The federation procedures are implemented and managed by a single, generic Federation smart contract (SC) deployed on the permissioned blockchain. This SC represents a dynamic federation SLA, ensuring the required QoS between consumer and provider domains. Each blockchain node runs the same SC instance and each line of code is executed simultaneously across the entire blockchain network. Service providers interact with the Federation SC through immutable transactions, which are permanently recorded in the ledger, serving as proof that all federation procedures were executed correctly. For further details, we refer the reader to deliverable [1].

FIGURE 8. DESIRE6G ARCHITECTURE ENABLING DLT-BASED FEDERATION.

3.4.2. DLT-Based Federation Implementation and Proposed Workflow

For illustrative purposes, we present an example scenario (see Figure 9) involving two ADs – a consumer and a provider. The consumer requests federation to extend a network service, either to expand its coverage area or address resource limitations. This service requires deploying application functions (AFs) or network functions (NFs) on the external provider’s infrastructure and establishing data plane connectivity (i.e., inter-domain link) to enable seamless communication between the two ADs.

As shown in Figure 9, each domain comprises its own infrastructure, an SMO layer, and a blockchain node. A private instance of a permissioned blockchain is set up, where all federation participants run a containerized blockchain node using Docker, forming a peer-to-peer blockchain network.

The infrastructure in each domain consists of one or more DESIRE6G sites, using Kubernetes as the default Virtual Infrastructure Manager (VIM), with interactions managed by the IML. The SO is the

responsible component in the SMO to interact with (i) the IML to coordinate network service orchestration and lifecycle management and (ii) the Federation SC for dynamic negotiation and execution of service federation, allowing for efficient service deployment across domains by exploiting underutilized resources. To ensure seamless interoperability, ADs access the Federation SC through a REST API.

FIGURE 9. EXAMPLE: DLT-BASED FEDERATION SCENARIO BETWEEN CONSUMER AND PROVIDER DOMAINS.

The proposed workflow for a single DLT service federation process is shown in Figure 10. We assume that all domains are pre-configured with a blockchain node to form the blockchain network, with the Federation SC running on it. Initially, the consumer AD runs multiple NFs as Kubernetes Pods. The workflow starts with the registration step, where the ADs register in the Federation SC through a single transaction using their unique blockchain addresses (see step 0 in Figure 10). In this transaction, the smart contract records information of the registering AD along with its service footprint. Once registration is successfully completed, the AD is ready to consume or provide federated services.

The consumer AD initiates the federation process by sending a transaction to the Federation SC announcing the desired service extension or additional containers (i.e., Kubernetes Pods) to be deployed (step 1). The Federation SC records the announcement as a new auction on the blockchain and broadcasts it to all registered ADs (step 2). To ensure privacy and prevent other ADs from passively collecting information, the consumer’s address is hidden in the broadcast. The provider AD, subscribed to federation events, receives the service request announcement and responds by submitting a bid-offer transaction, which includes the service price, in a reverse-auction format (step 3). The Federation

SC records the received offer and forwards it to the consumer AD (step 4). The consumer evaluates the offer based on internal policies and, if suitable, selects the provider and closes the auction in the Federation SC (step 5). The smart contract then records the winning provider AD, notifies it of the selection, and reveals the consumer’s endpoint (e.g., IPs, ports, protocol, federation network, etc.) to establish data plane connectivity, marking the end of the negotiation and acceptance phases (step 6).

FIGURE 10. WORKFLOW OF DLT-BASED FEDERATION SCENARIO BETWEEN CONSUMER AND PROVIDER DOMAINS.

The selected provider then deploys the requested federated service (step 7). This deployment involves the SO of the provider AD instructing the IML to create data plane connectivity with the consumer AD using the service endpoint details shared via the Federation SC and deploy the required containers for the network service extension in the federated network.

Upon successful deployment, the provider submits a confirmation transaction with details of the federated service (e.g., connection information) (step 8). The Federation SC records the successful deployment of the federated service and shares with the consumer the connection details and the provider’s endpoint (step 9). Upon receiving the deployment confirmation, the consumer AD establishes data plane connectivity with the provider AD and connects the initial containers to the federated network (step 10), starting performance monitoring (step 11). Federation is considered successful when

the containers from the consumer AD maintain uninterrupted communication with those of the provider AD.

The selection of the blockchain framework, the development of the Federation SC, the APIs for accessing it, and their integration with the SMO are currently in progress. The final methodology and detailed implementation of the DLT-based federation component will be presented in deliverable D3.3 [2].

4. Service Optimization and Assurance

The Multi-Agent-System (MAS) at the Optimization and Network Control Layer is mainly performing service optimization and ensures that the deployed network service meets the respective service-level KPIs. In this section, we first provide the specific workflows for MAS deployment and MAS-based service operation [17] [18] [19]. Then, specific details of the security solutions designed are given. Related developments and implementation in terms of standards are available at [22] [23] [24] [25] [26].

FIGURE 11 DESIRE6G ARCHITECTURE FOR SECURE DISTRIBUTED INTELLIGENCE.

4.1. MAS Deployment

Figure 11 shows an overview of the essential DESIRE6G components required for executing the secure distributed intelligence. The architecture comprises multiple DESIRE6G sites in different geographical locations, each equipped with local networking, computing, and storage resources. Central to this architecture is the DESIRE6G SMO layer, which oversees the orchestration and lifecycle management aspects of the NS, providing guidelines for the agents and enabling them to operate autonomously. Within the SMO, the MLFO determines the deployment locations and connections of agents. A security-

as-a-service (SECaaS) tool is used to improve the security of the agents by adding distributed attestation sub-routines for measurement and verification to their software. The SO is the responsible component in the SMO to coordinate the deployment, where the IML is in charge of the interactions with the local virtual infrastructure.

A blockchain infrastructure is also part of the DESIRE6G solution that sets up two distinct SCs. The first SC dynamically manages the measurement and verification functions of agents, enabling mutual remote attestation mechanisms between agents. This allows each agent to check the integrity of another agent in the system, avoiding a centralized, Deny-of-Service-vulnerable verifier. The second SC ensures a secure exchange of keys/secrets for inter-agent communications. It is worth mentioning that DESIRE6G architecture offers a multi-use case blockchain framework, which, besides securing the MAS, also supports a federation of services.

Overview of MAS Deployment

Figure 12 outlines the proposed workflow for the MAS Pipeline deployment, which includes the MAS agents, their initial mutual attestation process, and their connectivity. This workflow consists of four phases: *(i)* deployment of the MAS pipeline; *(ii)* configuration of protected agents through a SECaaS binary hardening tool; *(iii)* mutual attestation; and *(iv)* secret/key exchange. The workflow is initiated by the SO during the deployment of the NS (see step 0 in Figure 12).

The SO starts with deploying the MAS pipeline and requests the computation of the topology of a MAS pipeline given the relevant details of the NS, i.e., the location of the VNFs, the performance required for that service, etc. (step 1). The MLFO computes the optimal MAS pipeline and returns a descriptor that specifies the agents' deployment location, booting image, and connectivity. The SO then interacts with the IML components at different DESIRE6G sites to deploy each agent (step 2). Inter-agent connectivity based on a virtual extensible local area network (VXLAN) that connects the D6G sites is also deployed in this step, even though it is not shown in Figure 12.

Once the agents are running and connectivity is established, the configuration of the agents starts (step 3). In this phase, the SECaaS system processes the native agent software (e.g., x86) and improves its security properties by including measurement, verification, and communication subroutines. Through

this *wrapping* technique, SECaaS generates a reference measurement of the agent and stores it in a secure repository, ensuring its integrity for future verifications (step 4). The MLFO then deploys the wrapped images of the agents in the sites (step 5). Next, it creates smart contracts that will be used to record the state of agents during the remote attestation workflow and store the secrets/keys for the MAS pipeline (step 6). It also creates blockchain accounts for the agents, including a public address and private key, deploys smart contracts to the blockchain network, and registers the agents' addresses (step 7). This allows the MLFO to control access to the SCs and add or revoke permissions in case of MAS pipeline reconfiguration or detection of infected agents. Once the addresses are registered, the MLFO distributes the blockchain credentials to the agents involved in the MAS pipeline for interaction with the SCs (step 8).

FIGURE 12 MAS PIPELINE DEPLOYMENT WITH INITIAL MUTUAL ATTESTATION.

To face group attacks, where a corrupted agent verifies another corrupted agent, an initial *root of trust* (RoT) is established for the first agent verification. To that end, the first attestation is triggered by the SECaaS when the MLFO confirms that the MAS configuration has finished (step 9). For the initial attestation, SECaaS prepares a remote attestation plan and asks the agents to run their attestation sub-routines for measurement and verification (step 10). The resulting hash value from the measurements (step 11) is compared to the one stored in the SECaaS repository and if it matches the agent is verified. A transaction is created in the blockchain for each remote attestation, including the test result, the identifiers of the involved agents (i.e., measured and verifier ID), a timestamp, and the updated RoT (i.e., last verified agent) in the first smart contract (step 12). Once the NS operation phase starts, the SC automatically manages the remote attestation process through an internal function that receives a group attestation scheduling plan (the sequence of agents for verification) and notifies the RoT with the reference measurement of the agent, without compromising its confidentiality to other potentially infected agents. These steps are performed periodically throughout the NS lifecycle. Finally, the MLFO pushes to the second SC the key/secret that the agents need to use to encrypt the inter-agent communication through the VXLAN (steps 13-14).

4.2. MAS-Based Service Operation

Near real-time autonomous operation, where the actions are performed in the seconds scale, is a special type of network automation that requires the availability of new technologies and architectures to be developed in the control and data planes. One of the required technologies is that of pervasive in-band network telemetry (INT) to get accurate measurements of relevant metrics, including QoS, e.g., delay and/or jitter, of the services supported by the network. Recent progress on hierarchical telemetry architectures with distributed intelligence showed the great potential of using such telemetry data for efficient network diagnosis and decision making.

In this section, we assume the dynamic flow routing, as a use case of nRT network operation. Dynamic flow routing requires interaction between telemetry agents and flow agents in charge of making routing decisions. Among different routing policies, *multi-path* routing introduces flexibility in the design and operation of the network by allowing operators to split traffic demands into multiple streams that are

routed independently of each other to the destination. Moreover, routes might have different utilization costs, and hence, the percentage of traffic sent through each route is a complex decision that needs to be dynamically tuned in order to meet robust QoS performance with overall minimum cost. Precisely because of the nRT decision making required, we developed a DRL-based agent that decides the routing policy to be applied based on traffic measurements and the end-to-end delay observed.

Proposed Workflow

For illustrative purposes, Figure 13 shows an example where several traffic flows (F_i to F_k), each following a multi-path routing strategy, enter and leave a network at different packet nodes. In the example, traffic flow F_i (from R_1 to R_5) can follow three different routes with different costs, where p_1 and p_2 are multi-hop paths on the packet network, whilst p_3 uses an optical bypass connecting R_1 and R_5 through the underlying optical network.

FIGURE 13 EXAMPLE: DYNAMIC FLOW ROUTING.

We assume that traffic flows are *splitable*, i.e., they consist of a large number of sub-flows that can be routed independently. The objective is to find the flow routing policy that balances the incoming traffic of the flows among the available paths, so to ensure per-flow QoS, specifically E2E delay. Such a routing policy varies as a function of the incoming traffic of the flow and the network conditions, i.e., the traffic of the rest of the traffic flows in the network. Therefore, the routing policy decision making process is continuously carried out based on the incoming traffic and the E2E delay measurements that allow evaluating the quality of the decision making. Note that the state of the network is known, and it is indirectly represented by E2E delay measurements for the traffic flow. In this demonstration, we rely on

the INT functionality provided by the P4 switches to measure packet delay. Specifically, a P4 collector collects, aggregates, and provides statistics of the delay measured by the switches supporting the traffic flows. Once the P4 collector pre-processes the QoS measurements, they are sent to a telemetry agent, which is in charge of producing flow telemetry statistics that are sent to the flow agent deployed at the source node, where flow routing policy decisions are made.

The distributed system consists of several interconnected software components. Specifically, the *telemetry agent*, which is part of the distributed telemetry architecture, includes: (i) a telemetry collector that periodically receives telemetry data from the P4 collector; and (ii) a per-flow telemetry processor. The role of these telemetry components is to compute the required measurements and statistics that characterize the current QoS of the traffic flow, from the received INT telemetry. In addition, *flow agents* are grouped in a single module per location named *multi-flow agent*. For instance, if several flows f_1 and f_2 enter router R1, the multi-flow agent at R1 would include flow agents for both f_1 and f_2 . Note that one single flow agent makes routing decisions for each traffic flow. The *manager* running inside multi-flow agents has the role of collecting and distributing flow telemetry data and local input traffic data to the flow agents, as well as pushing the flow routing policies computed by flow agents to the P4 switch. Interfaces between agents and P4 systems are required.

The workflow for traffic flows f_1 and f_2 is outlined in Figure 14. Let us assume that flow routing policies are configured at switch R1 (see step 0 in Figure 14) to enable multi-path routing. Traffic input flow measurements are collected and sent periodically to the local multi-flow agent for every traffic flow entering in the network (step 1); the messages need to contain both packet and bit count for every traffic flow. Packet delay measured along the path is reported through INT messages to the P4 collector (step 2), which performs aggregations and computes statistics, e.g., minimum, average, and maximum of delay and jitter. Periodically, the P4 collector sends the computed delay statistics to the collector in the local telemetry agent (step 3). In addition, delay statistics are reported to a centralized telemetry system that stores them in a time series database (not shown in the workflow in Figure 14). The aggregated QoS telemetry message includes per-path statistics for every flow. The received statistics are then processed by each of the flow processors (step 4) that computes per-flow QoS telemetry measurements and send them to the corresponding flow agent (step 5). When flow QoS statistics are received in the multi-flow

agent, the manager triggers its analysis by pushing both traffic and QoS measurements to the corresponding flow agent (step 6).

An AI/ML algorithm, e.g., based on DRL, makes routing decisions, with the operational objective of guaranteeing that the E2E delay does not exceed a configured threshold (i.e., QoS requirement), while minimizing the use of the optical bypass. Routing decisions are gathered by the manager that eventually sends them to the P4 switch (step 8). A routing policy is defined as the percentages of input traffic to be routed through each of the routes. Internally, the P4 switch translates this policy into flow rules to efficiently perform packet forwarding according to defined percentages.

FIGURE 14 NEAR-REAL-TIME OPERATION WORKFLOW.

4.3. MAS Security

As discussed in the previous subsections, MAS security leverages blockchain with two distinct usages of (i) agent mutual and remote attestation and (ii) inter agent key share for their secure communication. Both security processes are independent technically. On the time basis, the “spontaneous” remote attestation workflow enforces that agents are remotely attested before they start processing, hence before the key exchange is carried out and the agents’ interplay with a secure communication channel. The process of agents’ attestation is described in the sequel.

4.3.1. Agent Authentication at Bootstrap

4.3.1.1 MAS Wrapping Phase

Once the MLFO has computed the optimal MAS pipeline and created agents (see step 1 in Figure 15), it sends to the SECaaS Wrapper (step 2) and start the wrapping process. It consists of improving security properties of agents by including measurement, verification, and DLT communication subroutines (step 3). Then it generates a reference signature and a unique identifier (AgentId) of the agent (steps 4-5) and stores them in a secure database (step 6). Finally, it sends back the agent with embedded routines and the identifier to MLFO (step 7).

FIGURE 15 ATTESTATION PROCESS CONFIGURATION.

4.3.1.2 Novel Spontaneous Authentication Scheme

We modified the initial workflow because it required agent remote attestation to be scheduled in a multi step attestation plan (see step 10 in Figure 16) and for which we needed to know the number of agents to be deployed, their exact location and the sequence order in which they should be deployed. In our new deployment sequence, we have solved this scheduling issue by implementing a spontaneous remote activation sequence, initiated by the agents at deployment, wherever they are. The spontaneous

remote attestation cycle is initiated by the agent prior to its effective execution, through an appended routine which contacts the DLT.

This sequence diagram in Figure 16 illustrates this spontaneous attestation schema, with the agent deployment and attestation process for agents using DLT and SECaaS verification. The MLFO deploys Agent 1 (step 1), which connects whenever it wants to the DLT (step 2). The DLT checks if Agent 1 is attested (step 3) and, if not, initiates the attestation by requesting verification from the SECaaS Verifier (steps 4-6). Agent 1 computes a fresh signature (step 7), which the SECaaS Verifier validates against its database (steps 8-9). If successful, the DLT records Agent 1 as attested (step 10) and designates it as the new verifier (step 11). The same process occurs for Agent 2, with Agent 1 acting as the verifier for Agent 2's attestation (steps 15-26). The DLT updates its records based on the success or failure of the attestation for each agent (steps 27-29).

4.3.1.3 Future Works

In future work, we will focus on scenarios where an agent fails to connect to the DLT or fails attestation. In short, we will consider what relevant reactions shall be taken in this case, being the interruption of the agent execution or reversely, only an information delivered to the SMO. We will study the security of the token delivery and notably how the token can be specific hence be used by the only agent which has just be attested. Additionally, we will explore continuous attestation through the implementation of a spread-over-time hashing mechanism, enabling integrity verification to be worked out during the agent execution without causing performance overhead. This development is a major progress, paving the way to continuous security without causing performance loss.

FIGURE 16 MUTUAL REMOTE ATTESTATION PROCESS BETWEEN AGENTS, SECAAS AND DLT.

5. Robust, Sustainable and Privacy Preserving AI in DESIRE6G

Implementation details of AI/ML components developed across different layers of the architecture (see Figure 1 and Figure 2) are discussed in this section. More specifically, details of AI/ML components within Intent Based Orchestration layer, Optimization and Network Control layer, and Physical Infrastructure layer are documented. It is worth highlighting that the AI/ML components in Intent Based Orchestration layer and Optimization and Network Control layer are related to non RT (section 5.1) and nRT decision making (section 5.2), respectively. In addition, the AI/ML components in Physical Infrastructure consist of algorithms that leverage fast physical layer operations, such as decisions pertaining to resource management, among others (section 5.3).

5.1. Non-RT Decision Making at SMO

In this section, we explain the Robust, Sustainable and Privacy Preserving AI/ML methods used for non RT decision making at the SMO. See [4] [5] for original articles.

5.1.1. ML-Based Assisted SLA Decomposition

A network slice can span across various domains of the network (such as the access, core, and transport networks) and may be implemented across multiple operators or infrastructure providers. As a preliminary step toward service instantiation, the E2E SLA must be broken down into specific SLOs by the OE for each of these network/administrative domains (hereafter referred to as domains) [4] [5]. These individual SLOs then facilitate resource allocation. AI-driven SLA decomposition is anticipated to be central to automating complex 6G business processes [45].

The OE system determines the SLA breakdown for each incoming service request, albeit with only limited insight into the current state of the infrastructure within each domain at the time of decomposition. Instead, the OE relies on historical admission control data from each domain, provided by local IML or software-defined networking (SDN) controllers, based on prior service requests. As

exemplified in Figure 17 in the context of DESIRE6G for the RAN/transport/core network, with an SLA involving the maximum delay for the E2E service. We further assume that SLAs with more stringent SLOs (e.g., lower latency, higher throughput) are less likely to be accepted, creating a partial ordering for SLAs and a monotonic behavior of service acceptance [46].

FIGURE 17 SLA DECOMPOSITION.

Several SLA decomposition methods employing heuristics have been studied in [47]. Authors in [48] present an E2E SLA decomposition system that applies supervised machine learning to break down E2E SLAs into access, transport, and core SLOs. In our previous work [46] [4], we tackled the problem with a two-step approach, which is a combination of machine learning and optimization-based solutions.

While the approaches in [46] and [4] have demonstrated success, they do not consider the inherent dynamicity of the system, which is critical for precise SLA management across network domains. This dynamicity is shaped by several factors, including variations in traffic intensity, shifts in user behavior, and fluctuating network conditions. As these factors evolve, the dynamics within each domain also change, potentially affecting the decision-making process of domain controllers. To address this gap, we propose an online learning-decomposition framework [5], specifically tailored for SLA management

in dynamic, multi-domain environments. This is especially well-suited for the dynamic DESIRE6G environment.

Particularly, we propose an online learning-decomposition framework termed Real-time Adaptive DEcomposition (RADE), which is capable of running stable updates of the model as well as providing resilience against noisy samples (see Figure 18). The following are the key components of RADE:

- **Base model:** Following the design in [4], the base model is an NN. To account for monotonicity, we employ Absolute Weight Transformation (AWET) approach that shows prominent performance. AWET ensures that the weights remain non-negative, a sufficient condition for an NN to be monotonic, while allowing the model's weights to be optimized freely during training.
- **Online update:** Unlike traditional static models, which are trained once and applied indefinitely, our approach involves periodic updates to the model based on the most recent feedback collected within each discrete time step. As illustrated in Figure 18, the loop begins with a base model and employs simple Online Gradient Descent (OGD) to perform updates. The continuously updated model is then used for real-time decomposition, ensuring that the system adapts promptly to the latest conditions.
- **FIFO memory buffer:** Updating the model solely based on the most recent observations can lead to instability. For instance, the model may overfit when the feedback data is sparse, or learning may be compromised if feedback data contains errors. To mitigate these issues, we propose using a FIFO buffer with finite capacity for storing feedback. The FIFO buffer ensures a more stable and reliable learning process by maintaining a portion of historical feedback alongside all recent feedback.

Note that the decomposition step follows the work in [46] and [4], where the sequential least squares programming (SLSQP) algorithm optimizer is applied.

FIGURE 18 ILLUSTRATION OF RADE FRAMEWORK.

Figure 19 presents the average E2E acceptance probability across different arrival rates for four methods: Static, RADE*, RADE, and OPT. The arrival rates vary between 0.3, 0.5, and 0.7 requests per time unit, representing different traffic intensities in the system. The Static method involves a one-time training of risk models, whereas RADE* is a variant of RADE that omits the FIFO memory buffer, and OPT represents the optimal theoretical performance, serving as a benchmark for comparison. The RADE method, which includes the FIFO memory buffer for maintaining historical feedback, outperforms both Static and RADE* across various arrival rates, highlighting the importance of the use of the FIFO buffer to enhance the robustness and stability of the framework, particularly in scenarios with limited feedback.

FIGURE 19 AVERAGE E2E ACCEPTANCE PROBABILITY VS. ARRIVAL RATE.

Figure 20 illustrates the average E2E acceptance probability for the RADE* and RADE methods under varying corruption rates (0.1, 0.2, and 0.3), where each feedback is corrupted (i.e., the request is always rejected). As the rate increases, the performance of RADE* significantly deteriorates, while RADE consistently maintains a higher acceptance probability across all corruption rates. This figure clearly demonstrates again that RADE is more resilient to corrupted feedback compared to RADE*, due to the use of the FIFO memory buffer.

FIGURE 20 AVERAGE E2E ACCEPTANCE PROBABILITY VS. CORRUPTION RATE AT ARRIVAL RATE=0.5.

5.1.2. Algorithmic Developments within OE

Design of the algorithms withing the proposed OE framework in section 3.2 are ongoing and are yet to be developed, tested, and implemented. A detailed discussion of the implementation is presented in the ‘Final report on the DESIRE6G intelligent and secure management, orchestration, and control’, i.e., D3.3.

5.2. Near-RT Decision-Making at MAS

In this section, we first detail the procedures for the flow provisioning phase, formally describing the DRL engine behind autonomous flow routing and the subsequent nRT flow operation [17]. Then we present the nRT elastic scaling methods [20] [21].

5.2.1. Autonomous Flow Routing and Subsequent nRT flow operation

Table 1 summarizes the notation used in the rest of the section, which is originally from [17].

TABLE 1 NOTATION (MAS CONFIGURATION ALGORITHMS).

Notation	Description
$x(t)$	Input traffic at time t .
$d(t)$	E2E delay measured at time t .
$s(t)$	State at time t .
P	Set of available routes for the flow.
k_p	Capacity of route p .
c_p	Cost of route p .
$y_p(t)$	Traffic routed through route p at time t .
$a_p(t)$	Fraction of traffic to be routed through route p at time t .
$r(t)$	Reward at time t .
$r_{delay}(t)$	Reward component for the obtained delay at time t .
$r_{cost}(t)$	Reward component for the routing cost at time t .
$\alpha_{delay}, \alpha_{cost}$	Weights for the rewards in the multi-objective reward function.
β	Fixed penalty for violating the maximum delay.
$dmax$	Maximum delay to be ensured for the flow.
$xmax$	Maximum traffic flow.
$pmax$	Maximum number of routes for the flow.
$G(V,E)$	Graph with the current network state, where V is the set of nodes and E the set of links connecting two nodes.

5.2.1.1 MAS Configuration

Let us start with the very first procedure that is executed at flow provisioning time Figure 21. Upon the reception of a new flow provisioning request (req), the SMO runs Algorithm 1 given in Table 2 to compute the set of allowable routes P . Algorithm 1 receives: *i*) the current network state, summarized in graph $G(V,E)$, where V is the set of nodes and E the set of links, and *ii*) the request including source s and target t nodes, maximum traffic ($xmax$), delay to be guaranteed ($dmax$), and maximum number of allowed routes $pmax$. The algorithm first discards those links with residual capacity below $xmax$ (lines 1-3 of Algorithm 1). Next, the k -shortest path algorithm is used to compute k distinct routes on the resulting graph G_{aux} (lines 4-8). The minimum expected delay $dmin$ (considering both *transmission* and minimum *queuing* and *processing* delay) is computed and used to discard those routes that cannot meet $dmax$. Finally, the remaining routes are sorted by multiple criteria. In this way, the returned set of routes includes those

with expected high QoS, while providing high diversity, so agents can choose among alternative options for nRT decision making. After route computation, relevant parameters to each $p \in P$, such as the routing cost and capacity are added, which are necessary for autonomous flow routing operation. Note that the complexity of Algorithm 1 is dominated by that of the k -Shortest Path (SP) algorithm.

FIGURE 21 FLOW OPERATION UNDER TRAFFIC UNCERTAINTY.

Next, the MLFO in the SMO initializes the flow routing agents, which contain the following modules (see Figure 21): *i*) the *DRL engine* as described below; *ii*) the *sandbox domain*, that contains pre-trained models and provides support for offline learning; and *iii*) the *analyzer*, in charge of evaluating the performance of models in operation and triggering model updating actions in case of poor performance. Once the flow manager is instantiated, the workflow (see Roman numerals) in Figure 21 is executed. The topology G , the set of allowable routes P computed by Algorithm 1, and QoS requirement d_{max} are provided to the analyzer (see I in Figure 21). Note that G also contains the maximum traffic volume for the background traffic that is expected for each packet link. Then, the analyzer requests to the sandbox domain an initial model (see II). Without loss of generality, we assume that the initial model has been pretrained offline, reproducing a network with the same topology G and routes P as those requested. A

generic input traffic, e.g., a sinusoidal daily pattern with some random variation, as well as constant background traffic according to configured maxima in G are also assumed. Note that to enable offline training, the specific traffic characteristics are not well known at that time. Therefore, the selection of the generic traffic must verify that pretrained models provide the committed performance when they enter into operation. Finally, the sandbox domain returns the initial model that will be loaded in the DRL engine before operation (see III).

TABLE 2 ALGORITHM 1. ROUTE COMPUTATION ALGORITHM.

INPUT: $G(V,E)$, $req=<s, t, xmax, dmax, pmax>$	
OUTPUT: P	
1:	$G_{aux}(V_{aux}, E_{aux}) \leftarrow G$
2:	for each $e \in E_{aux}$ do
3:	if $e.cap < xmax$ then $E_{aux}.pop(e)$
4:	$P \leftarrow k\text{-}SP(G_{aux}, s, t)$
5:	for each $p \in P$ do
6:	$p.dmin \leftarrow transmDelay(p) + qmin$
7:	if $p.dmin > dmax$ then $P.pop(p)$
8:	$sort(P, <'dmin', 'similarity'>, ASC)$
9:	return $P[1 .. pmax]$

5.2.1.2 Autonomous Flow Routing, Running in the Agents

Among different DRL techniques, we selected Twin Delayed Deep Deterministic Policy Gradients (TD3). TD3 is an off-policy DRL algorithm that uses a pair of *critic* DNN and an *actor* DNN that is updated with some delay. Hereafter, we refer to the set of critic and actor DNNs that run inside the DRL engine as the *model*. The model is in charge of dynamically and autonomously deciding which fraction of traffic is routed through each of the allowable routes P that can support the flow.

During nRT operation, flow routing agents compute the state, the reward, and the actions periodically (e.g., 1 sec.). Recall that $x(t)$ is the input traffic and $d(t)$ is the E2E delay, measured at time t (see Table 1). State $s(t) > 0$ is defined as the input traffic scaled by the average capacity of the available routes P , where (k_p) is the capacity of route $p \in P$. In particular, we have

$$s(t) = x(t) \cdot \frac{\sum_{p \in P} k_p}{|P|}.$$

Each action $a(t) \in [0,1]^{|P|}$ is a $|P|$ -dimensional vector, where every component specifies the fraction of input traffic to be routed through route p . Then, $y_p(t)$, the traffic routed through p is given by

$$y_p(t) = a_p(t) \cdot x(t).$$

The reward function $r(t)$ should penalize those actions that resulted into poor QoS or increased network cost. In consequence, a multi-objective reward function with two reward components has been considered to account for the obtained delay (r_{delay}) and for the routing cost (r_{cost}), being α_{delay} and α_{cost} the weight of each component. More specifically,

$$r(t) = \alpha_{delay} \cdot r_{delay}(t) + \alpha_{cost} \cdot r_{cost}(t),$$

where,

$$r_{delay}(t) = \begin{cases} -\beta - \frac{d(t)}{dmax}, & d(t) > dmax \\ 0, & d(t) \leq dmax, \end{cases}$$

and

$$r_{cost}(t) = -x(t) \cdot \sum_{p \in P} a_p(t) \cdot (c_p/k_p).$$

Considering that $dmax$ needs to be ensured for the flow, the reward related to the obtained delay can be defined as follows, where β is a fixed penalty for violating the maximum delay. Finally, the reward component for the routing cost is related to the proportion of traffic sent through each of the routes, as well as to the ratio of cost (c_p) and capacity.

5.2.1.3 Service Operation

Figure 22 details also the workflow for autonomous flow routing with delay requirements in a single domain scenario (see Arabic numerals). At every time interval t , input traffic $x(t)$ and delay $d(t)$ are collected from the source packet node agent and fed into the DRL environment (1). Note that $x(t)$ can be directly measured at the source packet node, whereas $d(t)$ is computed at the destination and sent to the source node agent. As previously introduced, the environment block is in charge of computing the current state $s(t)$ and reward $r(t)$ and sending them to the DRL agent (2), which is in charge of both learning and decision-making (3). Action vector $a(t)$, with the fraction of traffic to be routed through each

of the routes in P , is forwarded to the packet node agent (4). This agent is responsible for translating such proportions into suitable packet node routing configuration and of configuring the routing tables.

FIGURE 22 FLOW OPERATION UNDER TRAFFIC UNCERTAINTY.

The pre-trained model that is loaded in the DRL engine in the provisioning phase is smoothly improved online from the decisions and actions performed during operation. However, the uncertainty in the input and, more important, the background traffic can lead to poor performance. For instance, if the maximum background traffic is significantly underestimated, large d_{max} violation can occur, which cannot be corrected by online learning. Then, in order to overcome such issue, Figure 22 details the proposed workflow that runs in parallel to DRL operation and is intended to improve autonomous operation under traffic uncertainty.

Let us consider that every time the DRL takes and evaluates an action, it pushes tuple $\langle x(t), d(t), a(t), r(t) \rangle$ to the analyzer (labeled 1 in Figure 22). At the same time, the monitoring data $x(t)$ and $d(t)$ are also fed to the sandbox domain to tune the offline platform according to real traffic and performance measurements. Then, the analyzer block evaluates the performance of the current model and, if needed, requests the sandbox domain to provide an update of the model with a different configuration for the background traffic (2). The offline trained model that fits better with the new scenario is provided (3) and fed to the DRL engine (4).

The procedure for detecting poor performance due to background traffic misconfiguration (and how to correct it) is illustrated in Figure 23. The figure shows three different cases of operation that can happen from the same initially offline trained model. Let us assume that the sandbox domain, once the model is trained, can compute the delay range $[d_{low}, d_{high}]$, for which 95%-percentile of delay (d_{95}) is expected

to oscillate. Without loss of generality, we consider that d_{95} is computed every hour with the last 60 delay values measured each minute. Note that the delay range is computed by simulation as a result of autonomous routing actions and considering the aforementioned traffic assumptions, i.e., sinusoidal input traffic and constant maximum background traffic. The behavior of d_{95} in the sandbox is illustrated in the left part of every figure (labeled *offline*), which stays within delay range, as expected.

FIGURE 23 DETECTION OF BACKGROUND TRAFFIC MISCONFIGURATION.

Figure 23a shows a case where the DRL model has a valid performance during operation (right part of the figure). The measured d_{95} stays within the range, although it fluctuates more than that assumed during offline training (due to differences between real and simulated traffic and network state). Conversely, Figure 23b shows a poor performance case induced by underestimation of the real background traffic, which produces large delays, thus violating d_{high} . Note that, although in the example d_{max} is still guaranteed (not shown in the figure), it is identified as a poor performance case that will

trigger model update assuming an increase of background traffic. Alternatively, Figure 23c shows a case where the d_{95} stays below d_{low} , which is considered as an initial overestimation of background traffic. Here, new offline training with a reduction of maximum background traffic will be triggered.

5.2.2. Near RT Elastic Scaling Mechanisms

In DESIRE6G, effective scaling mechanisms are essential for ensuring performance, especially given the stochastic nature of traffic loads and computational resource availability [20] [21]. Elasticity, in this context, refers to the capability to autonomously adjust resource allocation as workload demands shift [49]. The objective is to maintain high service performance while optimizing the use of shared physical resources. Accordingly, we have examined the issue of scaling edge computing resources within the framework of a Cellular Vehicular-to-Network (C-V2N) service, utilizing the MAS approach in DESIRE6G.

C-V2X technology, introduced by 3GPP, enables vehicles to communicate with other vehicles (i.e., vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V)), road users (i.e., vehicle-to-pedestrian (V2P)), roadside infrastructure (i.e., vehicle-to-infrastructure (V2I)), and cloud or edge servers (i.e., vehicle-to-network (V2N)). In this work, we consider a C-V2N application supported by edge computing resources spanning multiple Points of Presence (PoPs) which are effectively DESIRE6G edge sites distributed throughout the metropolitan area of a city. The terms PoP and DESIRE6G edge site will be used interchangeably in the following.

Figure 24 illustrates the placement of vehicles' tasks to PoPs, and the number of CPUs allocated to support their respective requirements at each PoP. Both smartphone users and connected automated vehicles (CAVs) are connected to DESIRE6G edge sites. CAVs rely on V2N-based applications, such as remote driving and hazard warnings, which require V2N traffic to be forwarded and processed at the network edge to meet delay constraints. In the context of DESIRE6G, service agents may adjust edge resources dynamically (i.e., employing the DESIRE6G IML) to satisfy V2N service requirements under varying workloads. Our study addresses this elastic scaling challenge by examining (i) edge computing resources collocated with the base station associated with each vehicle [21], which can be found in D3.1 [1], and (ii) task offloading/placement across multiple edge servers distributed throughout a city's metropolitan area [20]. These two cases are interdependent. On one hand the placement of application tasks determines the computing requirements per PoP, which drive scaling decisions. On the other

hand, scaling decisions define the maximum available computing resources per PoP that is further used as input for deciding on task placement.

FIGURE 24 C-V2X SYSTEM OVERVIEW.

To this end, we first formulate the task placement and resource scaling decisions as a joint optimization problem, considering the latency constraints of the C-V2N application as well as cost-efficiency, in terms of the employed computing resources. The problem is initially formulated with the assumption of perfect knowledge of all future vehicle arrivals. To account for the stochastic nature of traffic loads and the availability of physical resources, we formulate the joint problem as a Markov Decision Process (MDP), assuming no prior information about future vehicle arrivals. We introduce a new DRL approach called DHPG, to support a hybrid action space that encompasses both discrete (which PoP to offload tasks to) and continuous (CPU resource allocation of DESIRE6G edge sites) actions, accommodating the different placement and scaling decisions.

Joint task offloading/placement and resource scaling problem has been extensively studied in literature [50] [51] [52] [53] [54]. Existing research can be broadly classified into optimization-based approaches (including heuristics and approximation), as well as machine learning-based approaches. To manage the

complexity of the joint solution space, these problems are often tackled in a decoupled manner or considered as static scenarios, which may, however, limit the solution space. In contrast, DHPG captures the interdependencies between these tasks within a unified framework and optimizes the long-term system performance.

Specifically, as shown in Figure 25, DHPG involves (i) a state encoder that maps the high-dimensional joint state into a compact latent space, providing a noise-reduced representation with rich information, (ii) this joint representation is shared across specialized action heads, allowing each of them to make holistic and well-informed decisions independently, and (iii) we introduce the probability-as-action (PAA) approach, which allows for a differentiable representation of the hybrid action space, enabling actions from different actors to be optimized jointly with a single critic. This unified optimization results in faster convergence by ensuring more consistent gradient updates throughout the entire network.

FIGURE 25 DHPG FRAMEWORK.

We compare the proposed DHPG approach to different SoA introduced in [21] [55], and [56] using simulations based on a real-world C-V2N traffic dataset. Figure 26 shows that DHPG and DDPG obtain higher average rewards by 13% and 2% compared to the one attained by Triple Exponential Smoothing (TES), respectively while Proportional and Integral (PI) and Constant (CNST) remain below TES with a decrease in average reward of 11% and 14%, respectively. Figure 27 illustrates that DHPG effectively allocates a minimal number of CPUs over time across varying traffic conditions while consistently

meeting the target delay. Notably, the CPU allocation states exhibit a greater degree of unevenness across PoPs, highlighting the effectiveness of DHPG in deactivating unnecessary CPUs and placing tasks to PoPs with sufficient resources allocated.

FIGURE 26: AVERAGE REWARD OVER 40 DIFFERENT TRACES OF A 5.5H INTERVAL.

FIGURE 27 BEHAVIOUR OF ALL SOLUTIONS AS THE NUMBER OF VEHICLES CHANGES OVER TIME.

We further utilize the theoretical optimal solution on a small scale to derive optimality gaps for the selected approaches. Table 3 presents the optimality gap achieved by DHPG in a small-scale scenario.

DHPG closely approaches the optimal solution, demonstrating an optimality gap of only 5.2%. In contrast, DDPG and other benchmarks exhibit optimality gaps exceeding 10%.

TABLE 3 OPTIMALITY GAP.

Algorithm	avg gap	avg #CPUs	avg load
Oracle	-	3.20	86.6%
DHPG	5.2%	3.23	90%
PI	10.4%	3.04	89%
TES	11.3%	3.04	89%
DDPG	12.1%	3.02	89.2%
CNST	77.7%	3.40	77.4%

5.3. Complementary AI/ML Algorithms

Complementary AI/ML algorithms that span over the layers of DESIRE6G architecture are discussed in the rest of this section. These algorithms are mainly related to the Physical Infrastructure Layer of the architecture, see Figure 2. It is worth noting that the implementations of some of these algorithms are presented as proof of concepts only, see D5.1 [57]. We refer the reader to references [27] [28] [29] [30] [31] [32] [33] [34], the original articles, for more details.

5.3.1. Distributed Edge Intelligence for RIS

Initial developments of the algorithms that have been evaluated empirically have been documented in section 5.1 of D3.1 [1]. It is worth recalling that our proposed algorithms are designed to develop NNs to perform configuration of RISs in a wireless edge setting [27]. In addition, the architecture of NNs is designed to handle the common model training deficiencies due to local dataset heterogeneity. Moreover, the AI/ML algorithms' training is conducted based on FL with intrinsic privacy preserving properties. In the sequel, the implementation of the related algorithms in hardware testbeds is presented.

Our implementation is spit into 4 phases:

- **Phase 1:** Implement the classic FL with locally deployed clients and a parameter server (PS).

- **Phase 2:** Implement the classic FL with geographically distributed clients and a PS (some clients are local, some clients are not local, and PS is not local)
- **Phase 3:** Upgrade Phase 1 to accommodate heterogeneity of the datasets.
- **Phase 4:** Upgrade Phase 2 to accommodate heterogeneity of the datasets.

Only the first two phases are completed. In the following, we present the details of Phase 2 only since it is more general than Phase 1.

Figure 28 illustrates the integration setting of Phase 2. Note that we denote by 5TONIC the hardware equipment located at Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, one of the partners. Moreover, all the non-local clients and the PS are hosted at 5TONIC. The client fraction of 0.5 indicates that during each training round, 50% of the total clients are selected to participate in the training process. This means that in every iteration of FL, two out of the four available clients are chosen to perform local model updates using their own datasets.

FIGURE 28 OVERVIEW OF FEDERATED LEARNING ARCHITECTURE INTEGRATION WITH 5TONIC (PHASE 2).

After each selected client completes its local training with data stored locally, it sends its model updates back to the PS. The PS then aggregates these updates to update the global model [27]. This process repeats iteratively, with the global model progressively improving as it integrates updates from the

selected clients across different rounds, all while maintaining data privacy since the clients' data remains decentralized. This integration between the non-local testbeds and local sites demonstrates the scalability and flexibility of federated learning across distributed environments.

In the provided setup, both the clients and the PS are developed as Python services. The communication between the PS and the clients is facilitated using WebSocket, a protocol that allows for real-time, bidirectional communication over a single transport control protocol (TCP) connection. WebSocket enables efficient, low-latency communication, making it ideal for scenarios where multiple clients need to exchange data with the server in an FL setting.

FIGURE 29 WORKFLOW OF SINGLE COMMUNICATION ROUND OF FEDERATED LEARNING.

Figure 29 illustrates the exact steps taken during a single communication round in the FL process. As shown in the figure, the PS is running the WebSocket server listening to any request sent by a user who needs to run a FL task. In step 1, the request is received by the PS which holds the information about the

parameters required by the server to run the FL task. An example of a JSON payload used in a request is shown in Figure 30.

```
{  "task": "task name" ,
  "host": "102.108.115.11:8200",
  "clients": [{"client_ip": "100.5.98.110:5000"},
              {"client_ip": "100.5.98.111:5000"},
              {"client_ip": "84.111.107.221:5000"}],

  "minibatch": 32,
  "local_epoch": 10,
  "learning_rate": 0.001,
  "clientFraction": 0.5,
  "test_minibatch_size": 64,
  "communication_Rounds": 250,
  "optimizer": "Adam",
  "loss": "Cross_Entropy_Loss",
  "data_folder": "RIS_Data",
  "test_folder": "RIS_Data_test"
}
```

FIGURE 30 JSON PAYLOAD IN REQUEST FOR INITIATING A FL TASK.

Once the request is received by the PS, the FL task is initiated at the PS. During this step, a WebSocket connection is established between the user device which sent the request to the PS where the connection will be held until a stopping criteria is met such as the number of communication rounds. The connection is kept in order for the PS to send intermediate results back to the user device for logging the performance of the FL training process. Each step is logged in the terminal of all the devices, including the PS, clients, and the user device, possibly for debugging or maintenance purposes. Figure 31 demonstrates the output log during the initiation of the FL task.

```
oulu@parameter-server:~/Project/Server$ python3 websocket_server.py
starting the PS server...
PS server started and running...
received a request for new FL task
Initial model deployment at PS (5TONIC)
```

FIGURE 31 FL TASK INITIALIZING BY THE PS.

Once the initialization is completed, requests for local training are sent to the list of randomly selected clients according to the given client fraction (step 2 of Figure 29). The WebSocket service of the clients is already running and listening to incoming requests from the PS. A WebSocket connection between

the PS and each client will be made at this point. An excerpt of the output log by the PS is shown in Figure 32 which indicates the initial broadcasting of model to the selected clients.

```
Broadcasting the initial model and hyperparameters to clients 5TONIC1 and 5TONIC2
current communication round 1
Broadcasting aggregated model to clients 5TONIC1 and UOU1
Received model updates from clients
Aggregating local models
calculated test accuracy at round 1 = 58.5
current communication round 2
Broadcasting aggregated model to to clients 5TONIC1 and 5TONIC2
Received model updates from clients
Aggregating local models
calculated test accuracy at round 2 = 58.4
```

FIGURE 32 OUTPUT LOG BY PS DURING TRAINING.

At step 3 of Figure 29, the received global model is updated locally by each client based on its local dataset for a specified number of epochs, incorporating the received parameters such as mini-batch size, optimizer to use, and loss function, among others. Once the client trains the local model, each client communicates the trained model weights back to the PS as indicated in step 4 of Figure 29. Figure 33 illustrates an excerpt of the output log of clients during the training and transmission of model weights.

```
Starting local model updating
Current epoch 1
Model update completed. Sending results back to PS
Starting local model updating
Current epoch 1
Model update completed. Sending results back to PS
```

FIGURE 33 OUTPUT LOG BY CLIENT DURING TRAINING.

Once the results from all the participating clients are transferred, WebSocket connections between the PS and each respective client are closed. Then as step 5, the PS aggregates [27] the received local models from all the participating clients to update the global model. Once the global model is updated, test results for the updated model are calculated and the aggregated model is broadcasted to the selected clients in the next communication round, see step 6 of Figure 29.. The process is repeated until a stopping criterion is satisfied. (e.g., the number of communication rounds specified in the request). At the end of each communication round, the test results will be communicated to the end user for logging purposes. Figure 34 shows the log output received by the end user during a particular training session based on FL described above.

```
Training epoch 1 completed at 5TONIC1
Training epoch 1 completed at 5TONIC2
Training epoch 1 completed at OULU1
Communication round 1 completed with accuracy 68.2
Training epoch 1 completed at 5TONIC1
Training epoch 1 completed at 5TONIC2
Training epoch 1 completed at OULU1
Communication round 2 completed with accuracy 74.6
```

FIGURE 34 OUTPUT LOG OF END USER DEVICE.

Once the training is completed, a plot of the results for training including performance metrics test accuracy and test loss (moving averages) will be available for the end user. Figure 35 illustrates such a plot of the results where training is done using our empirical RIS dataset described in section 5.5 of D5.1 [57].

FIGURE 35 TRAINING ACCURACY AND TRAINING LOSS FOR CLASSIC FL WITH RIS DATA.

Slight decrease in the test accuracy with iterations can be attributed to several factors, including overfitting and test set characteristics, among others, which will be further scrutinized in D3.3 [2]. Implementations related to Phases 3 and 4 are ongoing. It is worth pointing out that report [28] provides additional details and complementary information of the FL implementation.

5.3.2. Confidentiality Preserving Data Exchange with Third Party xApps

The analysis of data by a third party, with the adoption of rApps/xApps, enables ML as a Service (MLaaS) or cloud-based machine learning services. However, it also presents unique characteristics and challenges. The nature of the data whether it be images, text, numerical, real-time, streaming, or batch-processed- along with the criticality of response time require diverse solutions to ensure secure data transfer and analysis, preventing exposure during the process.

Data scrambling has been selected as a form of group-based anonymity for confidentiality preservation. This method strategically alters the arrangement of a dataset's rows and columns. In contexts where network data is involved, such as information from a telecommunications service provider, scrambling effectively conceals the specific details of signal degradation, including its location and timing. This ensures that the data remains confidential and incomprehensible to unauthorized third parties, while still preserving the ability to conduct statistical and analytical evaluations. Moreover, scrambling is a resource-efficient method that does not impose significant computational demands. Its lightweight nature allows for rapid data transfer and analysis, facilitating real-time processes. This is particularly advantageous when a third party must maintain online communication with the telecommunications provider to monitor the network continuously. This method has been preliminarily validated in an optical network scenario, where scrambled data are used as input features for soft failure detection based on unsupervised machine learning algorithm.

To detect soft failures in the data, we use unsupervised machine learning algorithms which do not need human guidance or beforehand training for data clustering [29] [30]. Data clustering can differentiate between the normal and different abnormal states of the network with grouping similar or proximate data points.

Figure 36 depicts the proposed approach. Following the chain from the left side, initially, the network state information dataset is collected by means of a Kafka-based monitoring framework [30]. The preprocessing phase involves reshaping the dataset into a format suitable for clustering algorithms, which requires time-series observations of all network elements. Each observation is documented as a

single row in the dataset. Subsequently, scrambling is performed in the dataset to maintain confidentiality. All the aforementioned steps are conducted at the network provider’s premises.

FIGURE 36 PROPOSED APPROACH FOR DATA EXCHANGE WITH A THIRD PARTY.

The scrambled dataset is then dispatched to a third party for failure detection analysis. The pivotal fifth block entails applying various clustering algorithms to the scrambled dataset. The third party executes this analysis and communicates the results back to the network provider.

The sixth block involves the transmission of the clusters of permuted results from the third party to the provider, who then retrieves the data in the seventh block to pinpoint failures. The provider, possessing knowledge of the network’s states and failure specifics, decodes the results to identify the failures’ locations.

Following Table 4 gives an example of data provided as input to our system.

TABLE 4 EXAMPLE: ADOPTED DATASET.

BER SPO1	BER SPO2	OSNR SPO1	OSNR SPO2	Amp1 Input Power	Amp1 Output Power	Amp2 Input Power	Amp2 Output Power	Amp3 Input Power	Amp3 Output Power	Amp4 Input Power	Amp4 Output Power
-16.8	-17.5	34.3	29.8	-11.3	3.9	-11.1	4	-12.7	2.6	-12.3	3
-16.8	-17.5	33.7	29.8	-11.2	3.9	-11.1	4	-12.7	2.6	-12.3	3
-16.8	-17.5	33.8	29.7	-11.3	3.9	-11.1	4	-12.7	2.6	-12.3	3

For clustering network states, we leverage the benefits of unsupervised machine learning algorithms, which do not require training with labeled data. This ensures that the third party analyzing the network never accesses the original, sensitive data, thereby enhancing confidentiality. We utilize Python scripts for the scrambling process and the Scikit Learn library for implementing clustering algorithms with

initial setups being consistent for each algorithm on each dataset. The initial parameter for K -means is the number of clusters. DBSCAN needs two input parameters: eps which is the radius of the neighborhood around each data point, and min_sample , the minimum number of points required to form a cluster. Similarly, HDBSCAN needs two input parameters; $min_cluster_size$ which is the minimum number of points required to form a cluster, and $cluster_selection_epsilon$ that is a distance threshold; clusters below this value will be merged. OPTICS needs one input parameter which is the minimum number of points to form a cluster as $min_samples$. Affinity propagation needs a pseudo-random number generator to control the starting state. Finally Spectral Clustering needs the dimension of the projection subspace as $n_clusters$.

FIGURE 37 TESTBED SETUP.

The network scenario, illustrated in Figure 37, involves two transmit (TX) and two receive (RX) transponders, operating with different wavelengths (channel 1 at 193.1 THz and channel 2 at 193.2 THz, respectively) transmitting over the same four optical spans. To simulate various failure scenarios, Failure Actuators (FAs) are deployed across all spans. Each FA includes Wavelength Selective Switch (WSS) and can produce three distinct failure types on each span: a soft failure on channel 1, a soft failure on channel 2, and a soft failure on both channel 1 and channel 2. Each failure is programmed to manifest separately within its respective span, enabling the delineation of 12 unique failure states alongside a single state of normal operation. Failures are transient like the simple network. These conditions are expected to yield 13 discrete clusters, facilitating the subsequent application of clustering algorithms for analysis.

In our evaluation, the performance of the proposed workflow is compared with a benchmark workflow that does not implement scrambling. This comparison is crucial to determine how data scrambling impacts the clustering algorithms' effectiveness. Evaluating machine learning algorithms is crucial to identify the most effective one. However, due to the vast size of datasets and the multitude of clusters, manually verifying clustering results against true labels is impractical, often assessed by confusion

matrix. To gauge the quality and validity of clustering outcomes, we employ both external and internal evaluation methods. External evaluations compare clusters to true labels, while internal evaluations examine the clusters’ intrinsic structure. Given that different methods have varying assumptions and limitations, and may not concur with the optimal clustering solution, it is vital to apply multiple evaluation metrics and interpret the results with discernment.

For external evaluations, we use Homogeneity, Completeness, V-measure, Adjusted Rand Index (ARI), and Adjusted Mutual Information (AMI). Homogeneity assesses if each cluster exclusively comprises data points from a single class, aiming for a perfectly homogeneous result where each cluster corresponds to one class label. Completeness evaluates whether all members of a class are grouped into a single cluster, with perfect completeness achieved when this criterion is met. V-measure is a harmonic mean of homogeneity and completeness, providing a singular metric. ARI measures the agreement between cluster assignments and class labels, based on the Rand Index, which considers the proportion of data point pairs correctly clustered. AMI quantifies the shared information between cluster assignments and class labels, reflecting the mutual dependence of the variables. The absolute value of these metrics ultimately ranges from 0 to 1, where higher values signify superior clustering quality. For internal evaluation, we utilize the Silhouette coefficient, which quantifies how well data points fit within their assigned clusters, see Table 5 and Table 6 for results.

TABLE 5 RESULTS FOR SCRAMBLED DATA.

Machine Learning Algorithm	DBSCAN	HDBSCAN	OPTICS	Kmeans	Affinity Propagation	Spectral Clustering
Homogeneity	0.926	0.901	0.873	0.821	0.992	0.739
Completeness	0.857	0.844	0.63	0.5	0.272	0.815
V-measure	0.89	0.872	0.732	0.622	0.427	0.775
Adjusted Rand Index	0.926	0.909	0.609	0.292	0.029	0.841
Adjusted Mutual Information	0.888	0.87	0.727	0.618	0.396	0.772
Silhouette Coefficient	0.705	0.715	-0.115	0.465	0.311	0.535
Average of Evaluations	0.865	0.852	0.614	0.553	0.405	0.746
Number of clusters	13	13	16	13	185	13
Number of noises	207	152	2999	0	0	0

TABLE 6 RESULTS FOR NON-SCRAMBLED DATA.

Machine Learning Algorithm	DBSCAN	HDBSCAN	OPTICS	Kmeans	Affinity Propagation	Spectral Clustering
Homogeneity	0.926	0.902	0.865	0.828	0.991	0.737
Completeness	0.857	0.845	0.616	0.505	0.269	0.811
V-measure	0.89	0.872	0.72	0.627	0.423	0.772
Adjusted Rand Index	0.926	0.91	0.595	0.295	0.033	0.841
Adjusted Mutual Information	0.888	0.87	0.715	0.623	0.388	0.769
Silhouette Coefficient	0.705	0.716	-0.105	0.471	0.273	0.588
Average of Evaluations	0.865	0.853	0.603	0.558	0.396	0.753
Number of clusters	13	13	16	13	218	13
Number of noises	207	149	2969	0	0	0

Overall, except for DBSCAN, all algorithm evaluations yield slightly lower scores in this more complex setting. The performance drop is particularly pronounced for *K*-means, suggesting it may not be suitable for complex datasets. OPTICS and Affinity Propagation continue to underperform, failing to accurately identify clusters. Among the remaining algorithms, Spectral Clustering shows improved results with scrambled data but is hindered by its time-intensive nature and inability to autonomously determine cluster numbers. Despite the close resemblance between DBSCAN and HDBSCAN, DBSCAN consistently outperforms, affirming its robustness in complex network scenarios.

From the standpoint of preserving confidentiality, the consistency of evaluation metrics between the original and scrambled datasets is a key indicator of effectiveness. As evidenced by Figure 38 and the accompanying tables, DBSCAN, HDBSCAN and Spectral clustering maintain high performance, suggesting they are better at finding clusters while even preserving data confidentiality during evaluation. This can be attributed to their density-based clustering approach for DBSCAN and HDBSCAN, which identifies clusters as regions of high density separated by low-density areas. Unlike *K*-means, which presumes convex-shaped clusters, DBSCAN’s flexibility allows for clusters of any shape, making it more suitable for our datasets. Importantly, data scrambling does not compromise the performance of these algorithms since it does not alter the underlying density and distribution of data points.

Consequently, DBSCAN and HDBSCAN yield consistent results with both scrambled and unscrambled data, ensuring the confidentiality of the data and its owners.

FIGURE 38 EVALUATIONS FOR DIFFERENT ALGORITHMS WITH DIFFERENT SENARIOS.

Identifying the correct number of clusters is crucial for detecting network failures, as it reflects the number of distinct failure regions. DBSCAN and HDBSCAN excel in this aspect, automatically determining the number of clusters with minimal input parameters, such as the neighborhood radius and the minimum number of points to form a cluster. Conversely, OPTICS and Affinity Propagation struggle to ascertain the correct cluster count, even with simpler datasets. *K*-means and Spectral Clustering, which require predefined cluster numbers, may not be viable when such information is unknown or variable.

5.3.3. Forecasting Element to Support 6G Operations

A significant aspect of edge computing is its role in minimizing latency through predictive resource allocation. As low-latency applications become increasingly prevalent, the ability to anticipate and

allocate resources before demand surges is paramount. Indeed, a proactive approach ensures optimal performance even during peak loads, catering to the needs of applications such as augmented reality, autonomous vehicles, and industrial IoT. By predicting potential bottlenecks or performance issues, the edge platform can proactively address these concerns, providing a reliable and consistent QoS for the defined use cases.

The Forecasting Element module aims at achieving this kind of behavior, while providing an extended flexibility in the type of resources that can be forecast. Such a module can be interfaced with the Management and Orchestration Layer and the monitoring system to provide forecast data useful for the service orchestration [31].

The module architecture, presented in Figure 39 offers a modular structure which can be used to address different forecasting jobs in parallel. It mainly interacts with the Kafka-based (or similar pub-sub frameworks) to retrieve metrics from one or more data streams (e.g., topics). The module then stores locally X measurements in the past to produce, through embedded AI/ML models, K measurements in the future ($X+K$).

FIGURE 39 FORECASTING ELEMENT ARCHITECTURE.

More specifically, the main components are the following:

- **Data Collector:** Collecting metrics from the resources from the monitoring system.
- **Forecasting Engine:** Implementing four different sub functionalities listed below.
 - Handling the database where the data from the Data Collector is stored.

- Running the different AI/ML models that can be used on the platform according to the input data streams configured for each job.
- Exposing the forecast data to a dedicated topic/stream of each job.
- Gathering forecasting requests through an API server, which defines the jobs with input/output streams, input/output features and the model to be used (that can be trained or uploaded).

Considering the execution of a forecasting job at time t , Figure 40 shows the data structures in input and output manipulated by a forecasting job. Each forecasting job receives input from a matrix of data. Each row of the matrix represents one observation of the samples retrieved from the monitoring system, including one instance of all the values to be fed to the forecasting model. Each row has a size of N and includes the main feature (the one to be forecast), labelled with f in the figure, and the additional input features required by the model (i.e., f_1, f_2, f_{N-1}). The forecasting job temporarily stores last K observations (i.e., from t to $t - K$) and generates one forecasting value (f_t) referred to X steps ahead $t+X$.

FIGURE 40 FORECASTING ELEMENT INPUT/OUTPUT LOGIC.

The module is completely written in Python, and allows different models to be used (e.g., LSTM-NNs, Gated-Recurrent Unit (GRU), and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN)). These models can be then trained using different optimizers, such as Adam, and at a varying number of epochs.

The development of the forecasting module is in progress, and it has been tested in a Robotic Digital-Twin scenario.

The forecasting of metrics has been used to enable the automatic scaling operations to meet a certain SLA. The scenario in which the forecasting platform has been tested involves the scaling in/out of a network function virtualization (NFV)-NS using CPU and memory usage as indicators.

FIGURE 41 FORECASTING ELEMENT PERFORMANCE IN A DIGITAL-TWIN SCENARIO.

As depicted in Figure 41a, the forecasted CPU (blue line) follows almost exactly the actual $t + 4$ CPU value (orange line), with slight detours. Furthermore, in Figure 41b, the forecast memory is depicted against the actual $t + 4$ memory. The memory occupancy is estimated with a very high degree of accuracy with respect to the actual value, with very few distortions in the forecast value.

In the next phase the Forecasting Element will be adopted to forecast the status of radio links, in order to anticipate radio issues and anticipate the handover procedures.

5.3.4. Algorithms with Theoretical Insights into FL over edge

Some theoretical studies have also been conducted to characterize the performance of algorithms deployed in FL network settings from a signal processing perspective. Specifically, these studies focus on *i*) the impact of inexact communication [32], *ii*) the characterization of step size scheduling [33], and *iii*) the effects of graph optimization within a distributed FL framework [34].

5.3.4.1 The Impact of Inexact Communication

We consider an FL setting where the coordination between PS and agents consists of two stages. The first is to compute a gradient for the underlying cost defined as a function of model parameters, possibly with errors in communication. This gradient (with errors) is used for updating locally replicated model parameters at each agent. The second is used for combining the locally replicated models over error-

free communication. The inexactnesses due to errors in communication (e.g., quantization, noise) permitted in our theoretical developments are more general than those in related algorithms. In addition, a typically used gradient boundedness assumption for the cost function is not imposed in our work. Furthermore, like many related algorithms, we do not require to conduct periodic averaging. In contrast, our algorithm only needs an intermittent averaging, where each epoch for averaging is determined by using a locally verifiable criterion at each agent. As a result, expensive communication overhead for error-free averaging can be reduced compared to the case of periodic averaging. Convergence of the algorithm is also established under mild conditions. Detailed implementation of the algorithm is available in [32].

5.3.4.2 The Characterization of Step Size Scheduling

We investigate a novel characteristic referred to as fixed gradient over rays (FGOR) of the conjugate function associated with a generic convex optimization problem that is to be solved over a federated setting. We show how the characteristics of FGOR, can be leveraged to devise a simple stepsize rule that can be prepended with SoA stepsize methods to yield more efficient solution methods. Numerical experiments are conducted to demonstrate that the proposed approach can significantly improve the convergence of existing methods while saving a considerable amount of communication overhead. The contributions are documented in [33].

5.3.4.3 The Effects of Graph Optimization within a Distributed FL Framework

This work addresses data heterogeneity and the need for uncertainty quantification, two common obstacles encountered in distributed FL systems. Fast convergence in a setting with heterogeneous data and sparse communication graphs is theoretically ensured without commonly used assumptions on the prior knowledge of the data distribution across agents. This is accomplished by integrating an optimization step for the communication graph of the agents, in addition to the local averaging. In the resulting algorithm, each agent locally optimizes in an alternating manner the agents' posterior distributions and the communication graph based on some notion of the information content of its neighbors. Numerical experiments are conducted to confirm that integrating the proposed graph

optimization will outperform traditional fixed communication topologies, such as fully connected and star configurations. The findings are published in [34].

6. Regulatory Aspects for Proposed AI/ML Approaches

The regulatory landscape for AI and ML is characterized by an emphasis on data privacy, ethical use, transparency, accountability, and the need for national and international cooperation in establishing guidelines. As these technologies continue to evolve, ongoing dialogue between stakeholders, including governments, industry leaders, and consumers, is essential to shape effective regulatory frameworks. Such frameworks could condition the assumptions and approaches currently taken in related research and developments, such as those in DESIRE6G. However, any relevant issue on this front in the project is not yet identified.

The regulatory aspects of AI and ML are evolving rapidly as governments and organizations look for addressing the challenges and implications associated with the deployment of these technologies.

The European Union (EU) has implemented the AI Act [58], which is considered the most advanced regulatory framework for AI so far. It includes several restrictions on large language models (LLMs) and mandates compliance and enforcement measures to ensure responsible AI use. The Act categorizes AI systems by risk levels, with stringent requirements for high-risk applications. These regulations focus on user consent and grant state agencies broad access to AI systems.

Key regulatory aspects considered so far are the following:

- **Regulation priorities:** Relevant regulatory priorities for AI include minimizing the impact on data privacy, ensuring that AI does not undermine democracy or human rights, and maintaining a “human in the loop” supervision for AI systems. These priorities indicate a growing demand for comprehensive regulatory frameworks that address ethical concerns and safeguard public interests.
- **Concerns Regarding Data Privacy:** Data privacy is a significant concern in the context of AI and ML. Regulations are expected to enforce strict guidelines on how personal data is collected, used, and shared, particularly in industries that rely heavily on consumer data. AI regulations often focus on ensuring that data used in training AI models complies with data privacy laws, including General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in Europe. This includes requirements for transparency in data usage and the implementation of adequate security measures to protect

sensitive information. This involves ensuring that AI systems handle personal data appropriately, providing individuals with rights over their data, and minimizing any potential privacy breaches.

- **Impact of AI on Employment and Market Structure:** The introduction of AI and ML technologies raises concerns about their impact on employment within the telecom sector and other industries. However, in complex scenarios such as those proposed in DESIRE6G, AI and ML can be seen as an enabler rather than as a substitute technology, thus impacting positively in this regard.
- **Transparency and Accountability:** Regulations are likely to require organizations to be transparent about how AI systems operate and the data they use. This transparency is crucial for fostering trust among consumers and ensuring accountability in cases where AI systems cause harm or make biased decisions. Regulatory frameworks are increasingly addressing concerns about bias in AI models. Companies are required to conduct bias audits and ensure that their AI systems do not produce discriminatory outcomes. This includes developing frameworks that allow for the tracking and auditing of AI decisions and ensuring that AI systems can explain their actions and be held accountable for their outcomes
- **Ethics and Safety Considerations:** The ethical implications of AI, including bias in AI models and the potential for misuse, are critical regulatory concerns. There is a need for guidelines that ensure AI technologies are developed and implemented in ways that uphold ethical standards and prioritize safety. Within the context of DESIRE6G, this could be more related to the impact on specific use cases making use of DESIRE6G architecture and capabilities. This links with the notion of responsible AI. There is a strong emphasis on managing AI-related risks from ethical and legal perspectives. Organizations are expected to align with universal AI principles, comply with upcoming regulations, and demonstrate accountability for AI systems.

7. Conclusions

This document is an interim report and an extension of D3.1 which discusses the implementation aspects of DESIRE6G intelligent and secure management, orchestration, and control. The documented content includes the development of the project from month 12 to month 23 of the project.

A concise discussion was presented to explain how artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) are aligned with the various layers of the envisioned DESIRE6G architecture proposed in D2.2. This was accomplished by first abstracting the functional role of each layer of the architecture to fulfill respective design requirements [D3.3]. Then, requirement-to-layer alignment was leveraged as the basis for choosing relevant AI/ML components tailored to meet the specific needs of each layer.

Following this, we documented the implementation details within three key areas. First, we discuss the End-to-End (E2E) Service Management and Orchestration (SMO), which is responsible for achieving seamless deployment and lifecycle management of services across a heterogeneous, multi-domain 6G environment. Secondly, we focused on the Multi-Agent System (MAS), which embeds distributed intelligence closer to the physical infrastructure. MAS has been responsible for fine-tuning network and computational resources based on continuous monitoring and adaptive control mechanisms, using AI to interpret telemetry data and make rapid, localized adjustments. Next, the development and implementation details of AI/ML algorithms that are deployed in each layer of the DESIRE6G architecture have been presented highlighting the key component and their functionalities with representative empirical results.

Finally, we examined the regulatory aspects associated with deploying AI/ML solutions in a 6G network context, considering emerging guidelines and compliance needs. Our initial investigations showed that the AI/ML developments within DESIRE6G at this stage remain aligned with evolving standards and regulatory requirements, promoting secure, scalable, and efficient AI-driven network management. However, more investigations will be conducted if needed to further scrutinize the compatibility of AI/ML components used in DESIRE6G with the regulatory requirements.

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